

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D2.3

The CoBraD ethical and regulatory framework

March 2022

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks/Changes
0.10	1/10/2021	Sergi Vazquez Maymir (VUB)	TOC contribution
0.20	15/12/2022	Sergi Vazquez Maymir (VUB)	Content update
0.30	28/01/2022	Francesca Morpurgo (CEL)	Contribution section 2.2
0.40	1/03/2022	Sergi Vazquez Maymir (VUB)	Content update
0.50	09/03/2022	Luiz Eduardo Mateus Brandão (UU) Francesca Morpurgo (CEL)	Internal Review
0.70	22/03/2022	Sergi Vazquez Maymir (VUB)	Integration review comments
0.80	30/03/2022	Michael Kontoulis (NTUA)	Quality Control
1.00	30/03/2022	Christos Ntanos (NTUA)	Final version to be Submitted

Table of Contents

LIST OF TABLES	9
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	10
1 INTRODUCTION	14
1.1 Purpose and Scope	14
1.2 Structure of the Deliverable	14
1.3 Relation to other deliverables/WPs/Tasks.....	15
2 THE ETHICAL FRAMEWORK IN THE MES COBRAD PROJECT	16
2.1 Introduction research ethics and innovation governance in MES-CoBraD	16
2.2 Research ethics in MES-CoBraD	16
2.2.1 The Research Ethics Framework at MES- CoBraD	16
2.2.2 Patient rights in the European Union	17
2.2.3 Informed consent and Pilot Use Cases (PUCS).....	18
2.2.4 Competent ethics committees.....	20
2.3 Innovation governance of ethics for the MES-CoBraD Platform	20
2.3.1 MES-CoBraD ethical challenges	20
2.3.2 Group recruitment and composition	22
2.3.3 The hidden biases problem	22
2.3.4 The Accountability issue.....	24
2.3.5 The misuse issue	24
2.4 Innovation governance of ethics in MES-CoBraD: The key requirements	25
2.5 Innovation monitoring of ethics in MES-CoBraD: The process.....	25
2.6 Innovation evaluation of ethics in MES-CoBraD: The key requirements	26
2.6.1 Accountability.....	26
2.6.2 Beneficence and non-maleficence.....	27
2.6.3 Transparency	28
2.6.4 MES-CoBraD vs Traditional Healthcare.....	28
3 THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORK: DATA PROTECTION IN MES-COBRAD	30
3.1 Privacy and data protection as fundamental right.....	30
3.2 Council of Europe and Data Protection	31
3.2.1 The European Convention on human rights, Article 8	31
3.2.2 Convention 108 and the modernised Convention 108+	32

3.3	European Union data protection law	32
3.3.1	Primary Law	32
3.3.2	Secondary Law.....	33
3.4	Member states and third countries data protection normative frameworks	35
3.4.1	Spain	35
3.4.2	Italy.....	36
3.4.3	Greece.....	37
3.4.4	Sweden.....	37
3.4.5	Third countries.....	38
4	CAPITA SELECTA: DATA PROTECTION and MES-COBRA D	39
4.1	Personal data and health data.....	39
4.1.1	What is personal data?	39
4.1.2	When is a data subject considered to be identified or identifiable?.....	39
4.1.3	Special categories of personal data.....	40
4.1.4	Data concerning health.....	40
4.1.5	What data is processed during the project MES-CoBraD	41
4.2	Data processing activities in MES-CoBraD	42
4.2.1	The data processing lifecycle in MES-CoBraD	42
4.2.2	Defining a data processing activity	42
4.2.3	The data processing activities in MES-CoBraD.....	43
4.3	De-Personalisation of personal data.....	44
4.3.1	What does anonymisation mean?.....	44
4.3.2	Anonymisation techniques.....	44
4.3.3	What does pseudonymisation mean?.....	45
4.3.4	Preliminary Assessment on the MES-CoBraD “de personalisation” module.....	46
4.4	Controllershship: Role and obligations in MES-CoBraD	47
4.4.1	Who is a controller?.....	47
4.4.2	What is a processor ?.....	48
4.4.3	What is a Joint controllership?.....	48
4.4.4	Distinguishing between controllers-joint controllers and processors.	49
4.4.5	Data processing responsibility.....	50
4.4.6	The processing arrangement for the scientific research performed at MES-CoBraD.....	52
4.5	Data Protection principles in MES-CoBraD.....	52
4.5.1	Derogations under the scientific research regime	52

4.5.2	Lawfulness of processing.....	53
	Explicit consent: (Article 6(1)(a) + Article 9(2)(a)), + Article 89 (1)	54
4.5.3	Purpose limitation: further processing and the presumption of compatibility	57
4.5.4	Data minimisation	58
4.5.5	Accuracy.....	59
4.5.6	Storage limitation	60
4.5.7	Integrity and confidentiality	61
4.5.8	The Principle of Accountability.....	62
4.6	Data protection by design and by default at MES-CoBraD.....	63
4.7	Security of the processing in MES-CoBraD.....	64
4.7.1	Data processing risks.....	65
4.7.2	Data breach, assessment and notification duty.....	66
4.8	Data subject rights under the gdpr	67
4.8.1	The right to information.....	68
4.8.2	The right to access the data	69
4.8.3	The right to erasure (right to be forgotten)	70
4.8.4	The right to restriction of the processing	70
4.8.5	The right to portability	71
4.8.6	The right to object.....	71
4.9	Designation of data protection officer and declaration of compliance	71
4.9.1	Designation of a Data Protection Officer (DPO).....	71
4.9.2	Declaration of compliance	72
4.10	International data transfers and adequacy decisions	72
4.10.1	Are there data transfers in MES-CoBraD ?	73
4.11	Data protection impact assessment.....	73
5	MES-CobRAAd as a medical device.....	75
5.1.1	Scope of “medical devices”	75
5.1.2	MES-Cobrad as a medical device	75
6	CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS.....	77
7	References.....	78

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 MES-CoBraD medical ethics principles	17
Table 2 MES-CoBraD Information requirements for research participants	19
Table 3 MES-CoBraD biases AI and innovation governance	23
Table 4 MES-CoBraD institutional guidelines and opinions on data protection	34
Table 5 MES-CoBraD Research Datasets based on D3.2 Project Manual V2.....	41
Table 6 MES-CoBraD Data processing activities	43
Table 7 MES-CoBraD Technical measures	64
Table 8 MES-CoBraD Organisational measures	65

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
C108	Council of Europe convention on automated processing
CIOMS Guidelines	International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans
CTR	Clinical Trials Regulation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPO	Data Protection Officer
Dx.y	Deliverable number y
EC	European Commission
ECHR	European Convention of Human Rights
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICH GCP	International Conference on Harmonization of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use.
ICT	Information and communications technology
Mx	Month x
No.	Number
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PUC	Pilot Use Cases
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
WHO GCP	WHO Guidelines for Good Clinical Practice (GCP)
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is a medical research project that has per objective the development of a platform equipped with algorithmic solutions and that offers medical practitioners a more efficient tool for the diagnosis of Complex brain disorders (CoBraD). During the pilot data acquisition MES-CoBraD will acquire Real World Data (RWD) in accordance with the protocols established in MES-CoBraD's Project Manual (PM)¹. The RWD of research participants will be stored in a central database developed as part of WP5².

As it will be observed in MES-CoBraD EU Law on data protection co-exist with the ethical and social dimensions of conducting research with human participants. The normative sources of these two dimensions are found at the local level, in national legislation, and in the norms that govern the functioning of institution-based ethical research committees.

With regards to MES-CoBraD medical research activities concerning pilot use cases (PUCS) that involve human participants, some key findings are:

- › When interacting with human participants, the principles of medical ethics, namely the principle of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice are fundamental and should guide the consortium when conducting the pilots.
- › Understood as a cornerstone of the principle of autonomy, informed consent should be obtained from all research participants involved in PUCS. This consent should be given freely, specific, informed and clearly reflect the participant's wishes. The obligation to obtain the informed consent of participants in a research activity represents a measure aimed at ensuring the protection of the right to human dignity and the right to the integrity of individuals, and as such, should be distinguished from the legal basis under the data protection framework.
- › Specific safeguards and protections should be put in place by MES-CoBraD to minimise the risk for vulnerable groups such as older persons, persons with chronic illness, including neurodegenerative diseases, who might be unable to give a valid informed consent.

With regards to innovation governance ethics, concerns arise from the exploitation of the platform, its acceptance by society and its potential effects to the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals. Some key findings are:

- › MES-CoBraD reflects in a new light question on regarding classical ethical principles of autonomy in light of the application of AI in society and healthcare. Similarly, there are issues that emerge connected to the accountability, the transparency, the group composition, and the presence of possible biases problems.
- › A framework to assess the conformity of the MES-CoBraD platform to the key ethical requirements is outlined – based on the Guidelines, developed by the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) on AI and on the WHO guidelines on Ethics & Governance of Artificial Intelligence for Health - and the key research questions, on the basis of which an ethical questionnaire will be designed and circulated, are briefly discussed.

¹ MES-CoBraD, D3.2 Project Manual-v2

² MES-CoBraD, D5.1 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – v1, March 2022

The MES-CoBraD project involves the collection and processing of several types of data, including sensitive data. Several questions around the nature of the processing activities performed during the project arise, some key findings are:

- › The source of MES-CoBraD personal data are retrospective and prospective real world data (RWD) collected by the consortium medical partners. The datasets include data relating to health and consequently qualify as personal data.
- › The MES-CoBraD project envisages several techniques to de-personalise its datasets. Whether the platform de-personalisation module pseudonymises or anonymises data will depend on its capacity to prevent the re-identification of data subjects. The de-personalisation of a dataset represents a processing activity in itself, and it is therefore subject to data protection rules.
- › In addition to the technical measures adopted it is recommended, that medical partners expressly commit to prevent the re-identification of data subjects using the data stored at their premisses.
- › It is recommended that the de-personalisation taking place at MES-CoBraD is considered a safeguard or safety measure rather than a derogatory ground for the applicability of data protection obligations.
- › From a controllership perspective, as some of the MES-CoBraD partners are jointly involved in determining the purpose and means of processing personal data in the context of the MES-CoBraD project, they will be considered joint data controllers. Nevertheless, when allocating controllership responsibilities, a distinction must be raised between the dataset controlled by the medical partner at the clinical site for purposes other than the medical research and the dataset uploaded and processed at the MES-CoBraD platform.
- › Provided the different level of influence in the project processing operations means and purposes, it is recommended that the extent of each partner's responsibilities are further detailed by means of a data processing agreement.
- › MES-CoBraD should aim from the early stage of its "architectural building," to be designed taking into account the observance of data protection principles and respect data subjects' rights and freedoms.
- › Due to the nature of the processing activities, it is recommended that periodic updates are performed on the list of risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects based on the progresses made in the development of MES-CoBraD. Also in this regard, it is recommended that the technical and organisational measures adopted to protect the personal data processed at the MES-CoBraD platform are equally reviewed.
- › It is recommended the project elaboration of a Handbook on Handling Personal Data Breaches.
- › Upon conclusion of the project and prior its deployment for exploitation, is recommended that a data protection impact assessment is conducted to assess the impact of the MES-CoBraD processing operations on the protection of personal data

With regards to the relevance of the EU Medical Devices Regulation to the MES-CoBraD project, some key

findings are:

- › Considering that the intended services of the MES-CoBraD platform might go beyond storage, archival, communication, ‘simple search’ or lossless compression, the platform could be considered a medical device, invoking the application of the EU Medical Devices Regulation.
- › It is necessary to separate between “MES-CoBraD as a research project” and “MES-CoBraD as the exploitable platform” as it relates to the applicability of the EU Medical Devices Regulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

MES-CoBraD is a scientific project that strongly relies on the processing of data from diverse sources, including data specially protected under the GDPR. Because of the sensitivity of the project's envisaged processing activities, the responsibilities and obligations of the consortium must be assessed side by side with the applicable ethical and normative frameworks. These frameworks must be understood as an "essential supporting structure" establishing the conditions and principles for the project ethical and data protection assessment.³

The deliverable captures the ethical and regulatory framework at the time of writing [M12]. It provides the main findings of T2.1 concerning fundamental rights for data protection as well as social and functional acceptance of the research activities in MES-CoBraD and the development of MES-CoBraD platform. In sum, two main objectives have been pursued:

First, provide the normative and ethical framework relevant to the consortium for the performance of its research activities. The ethical and normative frameworks outlined are aimed to help partners assess, anticipate, and mitigate the risks to research participants and their personal data throughout the duration of the whole project. Specific guidance is provided to the partners in order to conduct the research according to the ethical and data protection principles.

Second, offer practical insights and guidance for the implementation of the principles of data protection by design and by default for the development of the MES-CoBraD platform for a scenario of exploitation.

An updated version of the current deliverable will address any new or outstanding issues that appear as the project progresses.⁴ Also, specific ethical and societal considerations will be further flagged and monitored by partner CEL during the project and while the pilot use cases with human participants take place.⁵

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The structure and content of the deliverable is built upon VUB's experience and involvement in previous EU funded projects, in particular TenDER⁶, Nutrishield⁷ and PROTEIN⁸:

The second section introduces the ethical framework in MES-CoBraD. It separates between those elements related to research with human participants ("research ethics") and those that arise at the development and future exploitation of the platform ("innovation governance ethics").

The third section aims to inform the partners about the applicable data protection laws and national

³ Kloza, Dariusz, Niels van Dijk, Simone Casiraghi, Sergi Vazquez Maymir, Sara Roda, Alessia Tanas and Ioulia Konstantinou (2019) "Towards a method for data protection impact assessment: Making sense of GDPR requirements", d.pia.lab Policy Brief No. 1/2019, VUB: Brussels. https://cris.vub.be/files/48091346/dpialab_pb2019_1_final.pdf

⁴ D2.9 The CoBraD ethical and regulatory framework v2, due in M36

⁵ D2.5 Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards-v1, due in M18 and D2.8: Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards- v2 due and M35

⁶ P. Quinn, E. Mantovani, A. van Scharen (VUB), PROTEIN, D10.1 Report on security, data protection, privacy, consumer protection, ethics and social acceptance (TARESS Framework) (2019) ("PROTEIN"); Personalised nutrition for healthy living: Protein; <https://protein-h2020.eu/> (Last accessed 10 March 202)

⁷ D.Markopoulou, E.Papakonstantinou (VUB), D6.5 – Data governance and ETL specifications -Preliminary Version, Fact-based personalised nutrition for the young: ("Nutrishield"); <https://nutrishield-project.eu/> (Last accessed 10 March 2022.)

⁸ P. Quinn, L. Feirabend (VUB), D1.1 – Fundamental Rights, Ethical and Legal Implications and Assessment Affective basEd iNtegrateD carE for better Quality of Life: ("TeNDER") Project; <https://www.alzheimer-europe.org/research/projects/affective-based-integrated-care-better-quality-life> accessed 10 March 2022.

derogations applicable to MES-CoBraD research. Special attention will be paid to European Union (EU) law on personal data protection and the opinions and guidance notes from EU independent bodies.

The fourth section, titled *capita selecta*, identifies from a theoretical and practical approach, a number of critical issues to the processing activities envisaged in MES-CoBraD. Starting with the concept of personal data and its assessment the type of controllership, the implementation of data protection principles and data subject rights.

The fifth section considers the MES-CoBraD platform in light of the EU Medical Devices Regulation.

1.3 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES/WPS/TASKS

The conclusions and outputs of the present deliverable are, in general, relevant to all tasks and WPs of the MES-CoBraD project. This said, the following WPs tasks and deliverables are particularly affected by the D2.3 The CoBraD ethical and regulatory frameworks-v1 findings and recommendations:

- › WP2 on Legal, Ethics and Security Frameworks. D2.3 represents the basis for the D.2.9 and the updated version of the MES-CoBraD ethical and regulatory framework-v2; D2.3 also provides inputs to T2.2 The CoBraD PUC legal and ethical assessment and its results in D2.5, Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards-v1 and D2.8 Final Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards -v2.
- › WP3 on Landscape analysis & Methodology. In particular D2.3 provides the ethical and normative frameworks for T3.6–ETHAI model of AI in healthcare ethics standard development and its results in D3.8.
- › WP5 on Common multi-source research data lake & resource sharing and its different tasks and deliverables. In particular T5.1 regarding the data integration and harmonisation for heterogeneous data sources; and T5.2 and the development of the security and anonymisation requirements.
- › WP6 on Advanced Analytics and its different tasks and deliverables. In particular T6.1- and the specifications, requirements, infrastructure design and preparation for Expert System (ES); T6.3 and the implementation of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) knowledge-based system for data analysis and interpretation.
- › WP7 on Integrated Clinical Research Platform and its different tasks and deliverables. In particular T7.3 will take input from the architectural framework developed in T7.1 and will integrate the software components developed in WP5 and WP6 to form a sound MES-CoBraD platform.
- › WP8 on Pilot RWD Acquisition in CoBraD and its different tasks and deliverables, in particular T8.1 – Participant recruitment and pre-existing RWD access and T8.3 Secure RWD sharing.

On the other hand, the progresses in the above-mentioned WPs will generate inputs to take into account in updated version of this deliverable, D.2.8 The CoBraD ethical and regulatory frameworks-v2“.

2 THE ETHICAL FRAMEWORK IN THE MES COBRAD PROJECT

2.1 INTRODUCTION RESEARCH ETHICS AND INNOVATION GOVERNANCE IN MES-COBRAD

The proliferation of invocations of ‘ethics,’ especially concerning the recent debate on (the regulation of) Artificial Intelligence (AI), has been referred to as the “ethification” phenomenon. Ethics is often invoked to protect individuals against the disruptive effects of digital technologies on their rights and freedoms and to steer the development of such technologies in a desirable direction. Along this way, it is proposed as an alternative or complement to the law to regulate emerging technologies.⁹

As a synonym for moral philosophy, ethics is a branch of philosophy that deals, generally speaking, with “a rational and practical reflection on what is good or bad and right or wrong”.¹⁰ While the term morals refer to de facto habits, customs and traditions, ethics refers to a systematic reflection, a philosophical critique and evaluation. In the context of scientific research, classical ethics must also be distinguished from institutional ethics, namely those settings relating to policy, regulation, and research integrity or, more generally, politics.

The research activities performed in MES-CoBraD, involve different practices, actors, and institutions from various locations. In order to better approach the ethical elements of a multidisciplinary project, the ethical framework in MES-CoBraD is structured upon the distinction between “Research ethics” and “Innovation governance ethics.”

On one hand, Research ethics concerns the screening of project proposals or research activities that involve human participants, and it relates to the conduct of researchers themselves. In MES-CoBraD it focuses on the interaction between human participants and medical ethics and the role of informed consent in PUCS.

On the other hand, Innovation governance ethics applies to the research responsible for designing a technological solution. It is a way of governing technological innovation, while not directly based on legally binding norms, it aims to provide an advisory input for developers of the MES-CoBraD platform.

2.2 RESEARCH ETHICS IN MES-COBRAD

2.2.1 THE RESEARCH ETHICS FRAMEWORK AT MES- COBRAD

Research engaging with human participants must abide to medical ethics principles.¹¹ Through history the principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice, have been refined and developed by the medical community and codified in our language.¹² The principles are not absolute and must be balanced in order to strike a compromise between sometimes other competing interests. Normatively

⁹ N. van Dijk, S. Casiraghi, and S. Gutwirth, ‘The “Ethification” of ICT Governance. Artificial Intelligence and Data Protection in the European Union,’ *Computer Law & Security Review* 43 (1 November 2021): 105597, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2021.105597>.

¹⁰ Scholars distinguish, within moral philosophy between metaethics, normative ethics and applied ethics. The former deals with metaphysical, epistemological, or psychological pre- suppositions related to moral language, thought, and practice; normative ethics deals with the rational explanation behind the rules that would guide one’s action; applied ethics deals with the practical application of normative theories to concrete cases. Ibid.

¹¹ See D2.1 Legal and Ethical helpdesk.

¹² T. L. Beauchamp, J. F. Childress, *Principles of biomedical ethics*, Oxford University Press, USA, 2001 ; Walter, Klein eds. *The Story of Bioethics: From seminal works to contemporary explorations*; see also McLean S. *Autonomy, Consent, and the Law*. Routledge, 2010, Paperback, 248 pp

speaking they scattered in several diverse sources both at an international and national level.¹³¹⁴

Table 1 MES-CoBraD medical ethics principles

Principle of autonomy	Highlights the need to protect the patients and research participant autonomy. In that regard, informed consent constitutes a mechanism how patients and research participants can exercise their autonomy.
Principle of beneficence	The principle of beneficence requires a physician to do good and act in the best interest of the patient.
Principle of non-maleficence	Requires a physician to do no harm and avoid acting against the patient’s interests. It also requires the physician to “weigh the expected harmful effects of any proposed intervention against the intended beneficial effects.”
Principle of justice	The physician’s decisions about resource allocation require equitable distribution of medical goods and services. This principle also implies a prohibition to discriminate and warns the physician against making decisions based on negative stereotypes.

When considering the relevant ethical framework in connection to the MES-CoBraD research with human participants, a distinction should be made between research involving tests of medicinal products on humans and the observation of humans using medical devices.

Insofar MES-CoBraD does not intend to test a medicinal product on human participants, the EU Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR)¹⁵ is not applicable. Nevertheless, references to the provisions therein are considered as guidelines and good practices.¹⁶

2.2.2 PATIENT RIGHTS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

While the project does not seek to treat patients, they are acknowledged as the primary source of the RWD used for the research in MES-CoBraD¹⁷ Their status as patients grants certain rights at the EU level as set out in the EU Directive 2011/24/EU on the application of Patients’ rights in cross border healthcare.¹⁸

Much of the Patients Directive deals with the practical implications of cross-border healthcare, such as reimbursement of treatments and other relevant administrative procedures. However, and in line with data protection rules and the data subject rights, the Patients Directive also requires that healthcare providers give relevant information to help patients make informed decisions and exercise their rights¹⁹. In this respect, Article 4 (2) identifies a number of obligations for the healthcare service providers, including those based on Information Communication Technologies (ICT) solutions with regards to:

- › provision of clear information regarding the availability, safety, and quality of healthcare,

¹³ They have been already introduced in detail at D.2.1 CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk report v1, section 4.1.2 Identification and recruitment procedures Submitted in M6.

¹⁴ See TeNDER, D1.1 Fundamental Rights, Ethical and Legal Implications and Assessment; See also p. 18 PROTEIN, Baseline Report on legal and ethical aspects of human participation in research, personal data protection, human tissues and cells, and medical device p. 14.

¹⁵ The Regulation aims to ensure the EU offers an attractive and favourable environment for carrying out clinical research on a large scale, with high standards of public transparency and safety for clinical trial participants. Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC, OJEU L 158 27/05/2014

¹⁶ See EDPB, 23 January 2019, Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR) (ar 70.1.b)).

¹⁷ See MES-CoBraD, D2.2 Data Management Plan v1

¹⁸ Directive 2011/24/EU of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients’ rights in cross-border healthcare.

¹⁹ Ibid Article 5(d).

- › the prices,
- › complaint procedures and mechanisms,
- › information on professional liability,
- › measures adopted to protect the patient's personal data.

The Patients Directive further recognises the Member state's obligation to ensure the security of the data subject's fundamental right to privacy by subjecting its scope to the GDPR.²⁰

2.2.3 INFORMED CONSENT AND PILOT USE CASES (PUCS).

In medical research, the principle of autonomy translates into the requirement of obtaining the patient's permission for intervening on their body.²¹ For the consent to be valid, it must be informed.

Based on the judgement of the nazi war crimes at Nuremberg in 1947, the Nuremberg Code laid down 10 standards to which physicians must conform when carrying out experiments on human subjects.²² The first requirement was that of "voluntary consent".

More recently the Declaration of Helsinki adopted in 1964 and its subsequent updates, have elaborated on the notion of consent in medical research. In its current version, paragraph 25 and 26 introduces the notion of informed consent, emphasising the information to be provided to a participant in a research activity.^{23 24}

Today it is broadly recognised that the constitutive elements of competent judgement by the patient or participant and thus the source of an informed decision involve the following attributes:²⁵

- i. the ability to receive, process, and understand information,
- ii. the ability to appreciate the situation and its consequences,
- iii. the ability to weigh benefits, risks, and alternatives, and
- iv. the ability to make and communicate a decision.

The Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine²⁶, known as the Oviedo convention is the first international legally binding instrument in the field of bioethics. It provides a framework for the protection of human rights and human dignity by establishing fundamental principles applicable to health care, medical research, transplantation, and genomics²⁷. Jointly with its additional Protocol, they outline the human rights principles in biomedicine through Europe. According to article 5 of the Oviedo Convention, an intervention in the health field may only be carried out after the person concerned has given free and

²⁰ Patients' Rights Directive 2011/21/European Union Article 11 (2) a. Also, and while not strictly applicable to MES-CoBraD research its provisions on the E-health network might of relevance when it comes to deploy the platform (Article 14 (1) Patients' Rights Directive)

²¹ Garrett et. al., Health Care Ethics, Prentice Hall, 2nd Edition (1993), See TENDER D1.1, p.18.

²² British Medical Journal No 7070 Volume 313: Page 1448, 7 December 1996 accessible at <http://www.cirp.org/library/ethics/nuremberg/>

²³ In this sense, the Declaration requires that special attention is given "to the specific information needs of individual potential subjects as well as to the methods used to deliver the information." World Medical Association, Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects (June 1964, and most recently amended October 2013).

²⁴ Informed consent in research with human participants has been included in many other instruments, including in the ICCPR, CIOMS Guidelines, the ICH GCP, the WHO GCP, and the UNESCO Declaration.

²⁵ See for instance Guideline 19, CIOMS Guidelines, p. 62; Meulenbroek et al., Informed Consent in Dementia research. Legislation, Theoretical Concepts and How to Assess Capacity to Consent. See also Kosta, E. (2013). Consent in European data protection law. (Nijhoff Studies in European Union Law; No. 3). Martinus Nijhoff. See also Tender p22 European Geriatric Medicine 1 (2010) 58-63 ("Meulenbroek et al."), p. 58. ; TENDER p.22

²⁶ Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, 4.IV.1997 <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list?module=treaty-detail&treatynum=164>

²⁷ <https://www.coe.int/t/dg3/healthbioethic/Activities/Bioethics%20in%20CoE/>

informed consent to it.²⁸ By reference to this general principle article 16(v) sets out the conditions for undertaking research on a person, including that “the necessary consent as provided for under Article 5 has been given expressly, specifically and that it is documented. Such consent may be freely withdrawn at any time.”

The Oviedo Additional Protocol deals in more detail with the issue of informed consent in biomedical research requiring in its article 13 that all potential research participants are provided with “adequate information in a comprehensible form” and lists the elements that they should be informed of, including the nature, extent, duration of the study, risks and benefits of participation, the handling of personal data and compensation in case of damage.²⁹

Article 14 of the protocol then reiterates that “no research on a person may be carried out [...] without the informed, free, express, specific and documented consent of the person” and that “such consent may be freely withdrawn by the person at any phase of the research”³⁰.

Finally, in the EU pharmaceutical context, the CTR introduces in its article 28 the mandatory requirement of informed consent for the performance of clinical trials. Its article 29 elaborates on the formalities and different elements of informed consent.³¹

Importantly, it must be distinguished the requirement for consent for a subject to participate in a CTR and the requirements for a lawful processing of personal data under the GDPR. As indicated by the EDPB in its guidelines on clinical trials, the requirement of informed consent by the CTR must not be confused with consent as a legal ground for processing personal data set out in Article 6(1) (a) of the GDPR. Informed consent, in the context of CTR, is a safeguard not a legal basis for data processing. It serves as an ethical standard and procedural obligation.³²

In MES-CoBraD each institution involved in research with humans has and will use its own consent form and procedures. The foregoing indicates the minimum information requirements of a valid consent to participate research:

Table 2 MES-CoBraD Information requirements for research participants

1.	Research scope and funding of the project;	2.	The right to ask any questions;
3.	The voluntary nature of the participation;	4.	The incidental findings policy detailing what happens if something suspicious is detected;
5.	The fact that personal data will be collected, for which purpose and in which secured form;	6.	The possibility to stop participation at any time;
7.	Expected duration of the participant's participation;	8.	No advantage or inducement shall be offered;
9.	Possible risks and discomfort (if any);	10.	Ethics approval has been sought
11.	Appropriate contact details of the researchers.		

The adequate observance of the Project's obligations towards consent of research participants will be

²⁸ Ibid Article 5

²⁹ CETS 195 – Human Rights and Biomedicine (Protocol), 25.I.2005 Article 13 <https://rm.coe.int/168008371a>

³⁰ Ibid Article 14

³¹ CTR Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 article 28

³² EDPB, 23 January 2019, Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR) (art. 70.1.b).

further monitored and assessed in D2.5: Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards [M18] and D2.6: CoBraD Ethical and Legal Helpdesk report v2 [M18].

2.2.4 COMPETENT ETHICS COMMITTEES

In addition to international norms of conduct, medical research with human subjects is subject to the approval of ethics committees. In general research ethics committee “must be transparent in its functioning, must be independent of the researcher, the sponsor, and any other undue influence and must be duly qualified.”³³

The CTR defines an ethics committee as “means an independent body established in a Member State in accordance with the law of that Member State and empowered to give opinions for the purposes of this Regulation, taking into account the views of laypersons, in particular patients or patients' organisation.”³⁴

2.3 INNOVATION GOVERNANCE OF ETHICS FOR THE MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

Several distinct factors related to the MES-CoBraD project can cause ethical and/or societal concerns. We saw in the preceding section how the MES-CoBraD project intends to deal with the “classical” ethical challenges (the principles of autonomy, justice, benevolence, and non-maleficence, the problem of informed consent, especially in case of fragile or vulnerable, the recruitment of the participants).

The following lines will present the same challenges assuming a particular point of view, that of the implications of the application of AI and ML to healthcare in the context of the MES-CoBraD research.³⁵ How do the aforementioned issues change when taking into account also the Artificial intelligence (AI), and how should change the procedures designed to assess they are respected? For example, does the necessity and the content of the informed consent remain the same? Does the principle of autonomy assume a new nuance? What does it mean to respect a fair recruitment of the participants? Should we also consider how a scarcely meditated recruitment strategy could cause recurrent and at scale harm at worst and at least a malfunctioning of the algorithm?.³⁶

2.3.1 MES-COBRA D ETHICAL CHALLENGES

The MES-CoBraD project aims to address health issues that are overly complex, and that must be approached carefully from an ethical perspective. In the preceding paragraphs we outlined a research ethics framework that acts as some sort of beacon against the risk of adopting a not-fully ethical approach during the research performed with humans. But as we mentioned in the introduction, there is more in MES-CoBraD than the due respect of ethical standards and guidelines around research involving humans.

The MES-CoBraD platform is strongly based on AI, which in this context assumes a position of relevance because it is used for both helping clinicians to diagnose and decide an appropriate therapy and for spotting possible interactions and comorbidity scenarios on three major neurodegenerative diseases, with the possibility of anticipating a diagnosis that without the AI could be years to come. For this reason, MES-CoBraD opens the route to ethics scenarios that are strongly connected with those related to the usage of AI into society, and that will be examined more thoroughly in the D2.5 deliverable.

The current section will sketch out a template for the innovation governance and evaluation that we are going to use in the development of the MES-CoBraD platform, alongside with the research ethics

³³ CTR Regulation (EU) No 536/2014, Article 29

³⁴ CTR Regulation (EU) No 536/2014, Article 2

³⁵ Van Dijk, N., Casiraghi, S., & Gutwirth, S. (2021). The ‘Ethification’ of ICT Governance. *Artificial Intelligence and Data Protection in the European Union. Computer Law & Security Review*, 43, [105597]. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2021.105597>

³⁶ Morley J, Machado CCV, Burr C, Cows J, Joshi I, Taddeo M, Floridi L. The ethics of AI in health care: A mapping review. *Soc Sci Med.* 2020 Sep;260:113172. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113172. Epub 2020 Jul 15. PMID: 32702587.

framework.

In other words, we intend to outline an actionable framework for the assessment of how the MES-CoBraD consortium can minimise the ethical risks that emerge when combining health and artificial intelligence (AI). The aforementioned framework will reflect on several AI ethics problems as they emerge in relation to the development of the MES-CoBraD platform, from the group composition and the influence of socio-cultural factors to the transparency and accountability, from the hidden biases to the possible misuse of the platform. In WP2 we will dwell on the fact that the expert system being developed at the MES-CoBraD project will improve the diagnosis and care of diseases that do have an impact on and are influenced by social and cultural environment and factors.

To this end it is imperative, to adopt an approach that takes into account the influence that social and cultural factors may have on the diseases at study and so on the programming and training of the algorithm. We refer in particular to the so-called hidden biases problem (and as it is widely known, the social and cultural factors are challenging to capture and represent so they can be a major source of unrecognised biases), that may derive from various sources, and that can lead to wrong diagnoses or healthcare plans.

AI can be used to examine an extensive set of data and detect patterns or regularities, on the basis of which it can make inferences and make decisions. In MES-CoBraD, health data will be gathered from patients, both from people who have been taken care of in the past and from the participants to the research, and on those data the algorithm will make inferences.

Since the AI algorithm can only know what it is fed to it, the first problem is then related to the composition of the patients group. How does the composition of the group have an influence over the outcome of the algorithm itself? Are there any means to avoid that the composition of the group negatively influences the algorithm working and results? Have all factors, including the social and cultural ones, been taken into consideration?

Strictly connected to the group composition, biases are inadvertently introduced into the algorithm because of the failure to consider a particular factor, for example the influence of gender on a certain illness. But that is only an example: the problem of biases in AI is huge and an object of much dedicated research.

Biases can indeed be classified in numerous ways according to where we put the focus. Here we briefly list some of them, without in this phase having the pretence of being exhaustive and demanding a more complete coverage to the deliverable D2.5.

Transparency and accountability, are essential for trust but also raise ethical considerations: if in a certain system (e.g., a healthcare system strongly based on AI) no one can be deemed responsible, is it fair to adopt such a system? And adopting the point of view of the clinicians, isn't there the risk that they feel disempowered, marginalised, or deprived of responsibilities? Should we change the informed consent procedure (to take into account the role of the algorithm)? And does the presence of an AI undermine the respect of the autonomy principle (making impossible a full comprehension by the patient)?

And finally, there is the problem of how to avoid misuse of the platform, in the event that it has a commercial exploitation.

The next section will start dealing with the group composition and then examine the other aforementioned problems. Then a proposed template will be outlined, in combination with the research ethics framework, to assess how the project behaves with respect to the core ethical questions, both usual and in relation to AI and technology.

2.3.2 GROUP RECRUITMENT AND COMPOSITION

In the D3.2 Project manual, outlined in a precise manner the ideal group composition. However, it may be possible that for several reasons the manual's indications are not respected or that some factors, for example, the education, the gender, the social and economic context, the background, and attitude of caregivers, are not taken into due account. This may impede the algorithm from seeing certain correlations that a human researcher may see. Or it may entirely cut out certain diseases or diagnoses.

These are problems that do not emerge only because there is an AI at work. Before the advent of AI and ML in medicine, the group composition problem was present (as it is in every scientific study performed on a group or population), but the eventual issues that could arise in consequence of the group composition were dealt with by the (more adaptable) humans, not risking causing a massive, recurrent error.

2.3.3 THE HIDDEN BIASES PROBLEM

As it is widely known the use of AI in Healthcare can involve different kind of biases, from the presence of prejudices or preconceptions in designing algorithms to the occurrence of too many hypotheses to test and too little data to verify and distinguish them in the algorithms.³⁷

According to some studies, biases can be distinguished as statistical and social.³⁸ Statistical biases refer to cases where the population distribution of the available dataset does not reflect the real population distribution. In this case, an algorithm could produce a result that differs from the proper estimation of the real phenomenon. Social bias, by contrast, refers to the inequalities that can arise from suboptimal, therefore uncorrected results for established groups of the human population. This bias, also in a certain way, may be seen as deriving from a false representation of a certain group, arising during the data gathering phase.

A classic example is the algorithm used in the US care system to support health decisions. The outcome was strongly biased against black patients because it based its decisions on a factor (amount of money spent on a specific group) that was conducted to infer that because black people spent less, they were healthier and so less in need of care. The amount spent in their case was inferior because their income was lower than the corresponding group of white people.³⁹

Extremely interesting is also the classification of biases made by Cirillo, D., Catuara-Solarz, S., Morey, C. et al. , where biases are classified into historical bias (when it arises as a consequence of how “traditionally” a problem is considered, even if the data are correctly measured and sampled), representation bias (the “classical” one, when a specific part of the population is under-represented) , measurement bias (when certain data or labels are privileged over other ones because they are considered ideal indicators), aggregation bias (only a particular typical factor is used to group people excluding other potentially relevant elements), evaluation bias (when an algorithm is trained on a dataset too different from the target dataset) and aggregation bias (occurs when consciously or unconsciously a certain feature, convenient but not wholly or solely relevant, is used to train the algorithm producing discrimination or other unwanted effects).

³⁷ Panch, T., Mattie, H. & Celi, L.A. The “inconvenient truth” about AI in healthcare. *npj Digit. Med.* 2, 77 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-019-0155-4>;

³⁸ Norori, N., Hu, Q., Aellen, F. M., Faraci, F. D., & Tzovara, A. (2021). Addressing bias in big data and AI for health care: A call for open science. *Patterns (New York, N.Y.)*, 2(10), 100347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100347>

³⁹ Obermeyer Z, Powers B, Vogeli C, Mullainathan S. Dissecting racial bias in an algorithm used to manage the health of populations. *Science*. 2019;366(6464):447–53

Table 3 MES-CoBraD biases AI and innovation governance

Kind of bias	Example	Counteraction
Historical bias	During the COVID pandemic, AI has been extensively used for identifying clinically significant symptoms; but the AI systems had been trained on and used for extracting relevant information from notes that human clinicians had taken, notes that incorporate a particular vision, and maybe bias. In this way, when used in a new context (SARS-COV2 symptoms), they are likely to reproduce that same bias (David Leslie et al 2021). ⁴⁰	Check the training dataset, assess the outcomes of the algorithm against the independent opinion of clinicians, try to identify ex ante with a desktop research possible deviated visions or biases that could affect a certain medical area or practice and check the results of the algorithm against your findings (if any).
Representation bias	A classic case is that reported by Norori et al 2021 ⁴¹ , in which being black people less represented in the dataset used to train convoluted neural networks that look for skin cancer. This cohort has less probability of being diagnosed and so rightly treated, even though they are more at risk for that particular illness. Another interesting case is the one reported in Amit Kaushal et al 2020 ⁴² , where they found that algorithms trained on US patient data were disproportionately trained on cohorts from California, Massachusetts, and New York, with little to no representation from the remaining forty-seven states, thus strongly affecting the validity of the results when applied to the other 47 states.	Check the training dataset composition of each pilot (also performing theoretical research on possible biases, for example, derived by gender or by race, that could involuntarily affect the dataset composition). Apply de-biasing techniques ⁴³
Measurement bias	As is reported in Obermeyer et al 2019 ⁴⁴ , a notorious case is represented by an algorithm that, in the USA, used health costs as a proxy for health needs, causing a huge measurement problem and an obvious racial bias: black people	Check what data or labels are privileged if any and understand if they are over-represented. If yes retrain the algorithm.

⁴⁰ Leslie D, Mazumder A, Peppin A, Wolters M K, Hagerty A. Does “AI” stand for augmenting inequality in the era of covid-19 healthcare? *BMJ* 2021; 372 :n304 doi:10.1136/bmj.n304

⁴¹ Norori N, Hu Q, Aellen FM, Faraci FD, Tzovara A. Addressing bias in big data and AI for health care: A call for open science. *Patterns* (N Y). 2021;2(10):100347. Published 2021 Oct 8. doi:10.1016/j.patter.2021.100347

⁴² Kaushal A, Altman R, Langlotz C. Geographic Distribution of US Cohorts Used to Train Deep Learning Algorithms. *JAMA*. 2020 Sep 22;324(12):1212-1213. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.12067. PMID: 32960230; PMCID: PMC7509620.

⁴³ Mehrabi, Ninareh & Morstatter, Fred & Saxena, Nripsuta & Lerman, Kristina & Galstyan, Aram. (2019). A Survey on Bias and Fairness in Machine Learning.

⁴⁴ Obermeyer Z, Powers B, Vogeli C, Mullainathan S. Dissecting racial bias in an algorithm used to manage the health of populations. *Science*. 2019 Oct 25;366(6464):447-453. doi: 10.1126/science.aax2342. PMID: 31649194.

	who used to spend less were considered less in need of healthcare.	
Aggregation bias	This bias happens when the algorithm deals with a diverse population or dataset. In that case, if an approach “one size fits all” is adopted an aggregation bias is likely to occur. Herman and Cohen 2012 ⁴⁵ , exemplified this situation when they discussed how hemoglobin A1c relationship to average blood glucose could vary depending on racial and ethnic differences, decreasing its significance as the primary biomarker for prediabetes and diabetes diagnosis.	Check what aggregation factors have been used and assess whether they are exhaustive and/or applicable in the case at stake.
Evaluation bias	An evaluation bias occurs during a model evaluation when benchmarks are selected and used to evaluate an ML or AI model. As highlighted, for example, by Suresh and Guttag 2019 ⁴⁶ , if the chosen benchmark is not representative of the entire population, there is a substantial risk for an incorrect evaluation of the model, as in fact occurred with some facial analysis algorithms when applied to black-skinned people.	Check whether the algorithm was trained on the same data set or another one and if it was, verify if it can successfully adapt.

2.3.4 THE ACCOUNTABILITY ISSUE

Another risk is represented by the accountability of the diagnoses made by or with the help of an AI expert system^{47,48}.

In case of error, who should be reputed responsible? The engineer who designed the algorithm? The researcher or clinician who used it? And strictly connected with the accountability question there is the “black box” one: how can the clinician understand the reasons that led to a diagnosis? And how can the patient trust something whose working no one is fully capable of explaining?⁴⁹

2.3.5 THE MISUSE ISSUE

One of the fundamental ethical aspects of the application of AI to healthcare is the non-maleficence

⁴⁵ Herman WH, Cohen RM. Racial and ethnic differences in the relationship between HbA1c and blood glucose: implications for the diagnosis of diabetes. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2012 Apr;97(4):1067-72. doi: 10.1210/jc.2011-1894. Epub 2012 Jan 11. PMID: 22238408; PMCID: PMC3319188.

⁴⁶ Suresh, H., & Guttag, J. (2021). Understanding Potential Sources of Harm throughout the Machine Learning Life Cycle. MIT Case Studies in Social and Ethical Responsibilities of Computing, (Summer 2021). <https://doi.org/10.21428/2c646de5.c16a07bb>

⁴⁷Habli I, Lawton T, Porter Z. Artificial intelligence in health care: accountability and safety. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2020;98(4):251-256. doi:10.2471/BLT.19.237487

⁴⁸ Smith, H. Clinical AI: opacity, accountability, responsibility, and liability. *AI & Soc* 36, 535–545 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-020-01019-6>

⁴⁹ London AJ. Artificial intelligence and black-box medical decisions: Accuracy versus explainability. *Hastings Center Rep.* 2019;49(1):15–21

principle. In the case of the MES-CoBraD platform, it easily translates to the application of the platform beyond the purposes for which it was originally conceived. The first risk is represented by external attacks that, for several reasons, aim to influence the correct working of the system (for example, slightly modifying images on which AI systems base their diagnoses or creating fake content). The system should be protected against such events. Another possible and easily foreseeable misuse is represented by the use of a system like MES-CoBraD by insurance companies, for example, to foresee possible illnesses that would advise against insuring a certain person or also for doing frauds. In a dystopic but not impossible scenario, there could also be the possibility for a private company or even for the State of evaluating the opportunity or recruiting a certain person in relation to their possibility of developing certain illnesses.

2.4 INNOVATION GOVERNANCE OF ETHICS IN MES-COBRA D: THE KEY REQUIREMENTS

To respond to the envisioned ethical challenges and since the MES-CoBraD platform is extensively based on the use of AI, MES-CoBraD will adopt measures to ensure adherence to the European framework on Artificial Intelligence constituted by policy recommendations and normative documentation on the matter.

The EU's approach to governing innovation and ethics in artificial intelligence focuses on excellence and trustworthiness, aiming to boost research and industrial capacity and ensure fundamental rights. This approach aims to ensure that any AI improvement is based on rules that safeguard at once the functioning of markets, the public sector, and most important of all, people's safety, and fundamental rights.

Considering that, from a legal and normative point of view, Europe is now engaged in completing the regulatory procedure of adopting an AI regulation (Proposal COM/2021/206) that will lay down harmonisation rules on artificial intelligence, but that has not come to a conclusion still, the project will follow the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI (Guidelines 2019)⁵⁰ to offer guidance on the innovation governance in MES-CoBraD.

The Guidelines, developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI, offer a good framework of seven different key ethical requirements that can be applicable to different stakeholders partaking in AI systems' life cycle. The list of requirements includes systemic, individual, and societal aspects, and they are human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, societal and environmental wellbeing, accountability

At a general level, we will assess MES-CoBraD results against these 7 key requirements ensuring that they are correctly accounted for and represented.

But of course, since we are dealing with AI as applied to a particular domain, which has its specificities, we will also take into account the recently released WHO guidelines on Ethics & Governance of Artificial Intelligence for Health (2021) which offers a vertical view on the topic.

The WHO expert group identified six core principles: (1) Protect autonomy; (2) Promote human wellbeing, human safety, and the public interest; (3) Ensure transparency, explainability, and intelligibility; (4) Foster responsibility and accountability; (5) Ensure inclusiveness and equity; (6) Promote AI that is responsive and sustainable.

As we mentioned before, more details will be added to the D2.5 deliverable.

2.5 INNOVATION MONITORING OF ETHICS IN MES-COBRA D: THE PROCESS

During the project, the conformity to these ethical requirements will be checked. It will be verified the applicability of the AI Guidelines and of the WHO principles to the MES-CoBraD project. This will be

⁵⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/177365>

accomplished with different actions:

- › Supporting the design process of AI solutions, trying to offer to the partners, where possible, *privacy- and ethics-by-design options* that can improve the trustworthiness and the social acceptability of the MES-CoBraD system.
- › Extract from this deliverable an infographic and an ethics how-to so that alongside with the Legal and Ethics Helpdesk participants to the project can quickly refer to it if they have doubts
- › Defining and circulating an internal *ethics questionnaire* to measure the correspondence of technical advancements with the requirements.
- › *Reports* during the monthly meetings for monitoring the ethics risk.
- › Direct explanatory connections between these actions and the “*Legal and Ethics Helpdesk*”: the helpdesk constitutes the informative interface containing solutions and suggestions for partners to mitigate any detected ethics risk. The helpdesk is the focus of deliverables D2.1 and D2.6.

2.6 INNOVATION EVALUATION OF ETHICS IN MES-COBRA D: THE KEY REQUIREMENTS

The compliance of the MES-CoBraD research and platform will be evaluated against what came out from both the ethical research and the ethical innovation framework. We will adopt an evaluation template that considers all the aspects mentioned earlier and that is inspired mainly by the work of Morley J. et al 2020.⁵¹

From this framework and our surveys and research results, we extracted a number of research questions listed and categorised below, which will be used as a guideline to define the ethical compliance template. Some questions, as you may expect, fall under the accountability, transparency, and absence of biases categories, but other ones, even if they take into account questions that emerge concerning the use of AI in healthcare, are more at the edge and could also apply if we were not talking about AI at all. In other words, the use of AI in healthcare not only brings to light new questions, but forces us to reconsider issues, such as the comprehensibility or the transparency of medical decisions, that in the case of human healthcare professionals, we take for granted, but that is far from being clear⁵².

Below, the main questions outlined by Morley J. et al 2020⁵³ are categorised according to the issues they are involved. Based on them, we will then define some reference questions that will be the ground floor for an ethical questionnaire to be circulated in the next project months. Those questions will be refined and will be part of the ethical assessment of the AI system that will be presented in D2.5.

2.6.1 ACCOUNTABILITY

Especially when dealing with health issues the accountability is absolutely fundamental, of course not only when AI is implied. But when we add AI to the usual accountability issues, things become even more complicated because it is objectively hard to disentangle the responsibility chain and also because people (both clinicians and patients) may feel that the presence of AI places the burden of the responsibility elsewhere. Even if the final decision pertains to the clinician, framework conditions can strongly influence it (e.g. the clinician workload, the reliance of the workplace on automation, etc), and an essential part

⁵¹ Morley J, Machado CCV, Burr C, Cows J, Joshi I, Taddeo M, Floridi L. The ethics of AI in health care: A mapping review. Soc Sci Med. 2020 Sep;260:113172. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113172. Epub 2020 Jul 15. PMID: 32702587.

⁵² London AJ. Artificial Intelligence and Black-Box Medical Decisions: Accuracy versus Explainability. Hastings Cent Rep. 2019 Jan;49(1):15-21. doi: 10.1002/hast.973. PMID: 30790315.

⁵³ Supra 50

(the interpretation of data) is in any case delegated to the system, making it questionable the extent to which we can say that full responsibility for a certain decision applies⁵⁴. If the clinician tries to form her own judgement, the usefulness of the system is at stake, while if she relies on the system's judgement, she cannot be considered to be fully accountable. Also, usual safety cases (a safety case explains why a system is acceptably safe to operate as intended in a defined environment) must be challenged and changed accordingly to the new ethical conditions. And they cannot consider the system alone, but the system plus the clinician and their interaction.

During the following months, an accountability model for MES-CoBraD will be developed, based partly on theoretical research and partly on questionnaires and focus groups, where the following questions will be exploited, examined, and used as a starting point to develop questionnaires aimed both at researchers and at clinicians and patients.

1. Are there any tasks that should not be delegated to MES-CoBraD?
2. Would it be necessary and/or possible to specify a definite chain of responsibility for decisions made with the help of MES-CoBraD? How could we enable people to report and seek redress for MES-CoBraD associated harms?
3. Should the system be entitled to perform autonomous diagnoses and healthcare decisions?
4. How can the explainability and accountability of MES-CoBraD diagnoses and decisions be guaranteed?

2.6.2 BENEFICENCE AND NON-MALEFICENCE

Beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and human autonomy are classical bioethical principles⁵⁵, to which when dealing with AI in healthcare, we must add explicability, which implies both intelligibility and accountability⁵⁶. Each of them implies several ethical aspects that are not exclusive to the AI healthcare area, but when AI is implied assume new nuances. In fact, they integrate all the categories detailed here (e.g the problem of justice is obviously connected to the presence of possible biases). The literature on this is really vast. Here we focus in particular on the system usage by the clinicians, in other words, we focus on practical problems connected with MES-CoBraD application, and we question ourselves about possible harm or negative side consequences deriving from a non-sufficiently expert use of the platform. Can a system like MES-CoBraD do everything a human can do? And do the humans that have to interact with it need special training (to avoid the risk of harm due to unskillfulness)? What kind of misuse could derive (voluntarily or not) from the platform application, and what barriers can we pose to it? And in case harm happens, should special processes to seek redress be studied, different from the ones in force with traditional medicine? We will, in this case, adopt the following research question as our starting point:

5. What skills would the professional healthcare workforce require to make safe and effective use of MES-CoBraD solution in the future? Do you think that a form of (ethical, non-technical) training of clinicians is necessary to avoid potential unintentional damage to the patients?
6. Which are the tasks that MES-CoBraD has been conceived for doing? Why those and not others? Are there any areas where the use of MES-CoBraD should be prohibited?
7. How does MES-CoBraD challenge bioethical concepts (beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, and justice)?⁵⁷

⁵⁴ Habli I, Lawton T, Porter Z. Artificial intelligence in health care: accountability and safety. 2020

⁵⁵ Beauchamp & Childress, J. F. (2012). Principles of biomedical ethics. New York, Oxford University Press.

⁵⁶ Floridi, L., & Cowls, J. (2019). A Unified Framework of Five Principles for AI in Society. Harvard Data Science Review, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.8cd550d1>

⁵⁷ Ibid 55 Beauchamp & Childress, 2012

8. What kind of mechanisms could be put in place to allow patients to seek redress from possible harm suffered in consequence of MES-CoBraD application? Should they be different from those used in case of “usual” non-MES-CoBraD clinicians?
9. Usually, health care systems are assessed in terms of efficiency, efficacy, and cost-effectiveness. Do you think that we should aim and that it would be possible to aim for a system that also incorporates the concept of social justice? Do you believe that a system like MES-CoBraD could have negative implications for social justice, inadvertently undermining people’s health, or well-being, or increasing disparities in access to social and health service structures?

2.6.3 TRANSPARENCY

Any system based on AI that has an impact on citizens' lives must provide access to its internal working and decision structures. In this respect, there surely is a problem regarding the transparency of the MES-CoBraD system in particular, but that, as pointed out for example by London, A.J. 2019, does not greatly differ from opaqueness in medical decisions taken by humans on the basis of the models they adhere and of their bodies of knowledge and experience. Maybe a fundamental difference may be seen in the ability of humans, if requested, to explain and justify their conclusions. In this regard, a possible solution could be to implement in the system a function that explains the “reasoning” that brought to a certain conclusion. Other measures to audit the system’s outputs or to make its decision-making process more transparent could also and probably should be studied and implemented. That will be the object of the V2 of this deliverable. We will start assessing the clinicians, the researchers, and the patients point of views on this point.

10. How can the explainability of MES-CoBraD solution be guaranteed? Is it possible to explain why given certain conditions it gives certain results?
11. How can we guarantee transparency over how algorithmic tools are integrated into the healthcare workflow, shape decisions, and affect process optimization within medical services?
12. Is the opaqueness of the MES-CoBraD decisions genuinely different from that of human clinicians? Why? Why is the algorithm considered a black box and the clinician’s mind it is not?

2.6.4 MES-COBRA D VS TRADITIONAL HEALTHCARE

What advantages does using a system as MES-CoBraD bring? Does using it bring a risk of undermining human patients’ fundamental rights more than what happens with “traditional” non-AI-assisted medicine? Is there an appreciable difference in explainability and accountability with respect to traditional medicine? And how can researchers overcome this problem when designing a system?

13. Do you think there is an appreciable difference in transparency between the decisions of the clinicians and those of MES-CoBraD platform?
14. Which tasks should be delegated to the MES-CoBraD solution, and which should not?
15. What evidence is needed to ‘prove’ the clinical effectiveness of an MES-CoBraD solution/diagnosis?
16. How can the explainability of MES-CoBraD solution be guaranteed? Is the MES-CoBraD system more “obscure” than the clinician’s mind and decisions?
17. What is the added value of MES-CoBraD with respect to classical clinical practice?
18. Could MES-CoBraD represent a source of discrimination or a barrier (meaning that for some reason, clinicians and/or patients do not manage to use it)?

As outlined before, the problem of biases is one of the major ethical concerns of AI as applied to healthcare. We outlined before the main points characterising the biases in the AI problem. In the case of MES-CoBraD, all the issues expressed before are relevant, but of particular importance is the problem of the data sets used for training the algorithm, that in this case is extremely relevant because MES-CoBraD deals with diseases that are not easily diagnosed and treated, also because of the strong influence on them of the socio-economic-cultural context and of the difficulty in having an objective view from laboratory analyses. In this case, we are going to adopt the following questions:

19. Is it important to ensure that all relevant stakeholder views are included in the development of MES-CoBraD solutions? And how can we guarantee that?
20. How can traditional and non-traditional health data sources be incorporated into MES-CoBraD decision-making? How can we ensure an adequate variety in datasets?
21. Do you think there could be a problem in assuring equity? For example, could there be racial and/or sex and gender biases involuntarily built into the algorithm? How should the risk of algorithmic bias be addressed?
22. Are there any de-biasing strategies and techniques applied?

3 THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORK: DATA PROTECTION IN MES-COBRA D

This section aims to inform the partners about the applicable data protection laws and national derogations applicable to MES-CoBraD research, both with regards to its activities involving human participants and also in relation to the development and design of the MES-CoBraD platform. Special attention will be paid to EU law on personal data protection and the opinions and guidance notes from EU independent bodies.

3.1 PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION AS FUNDAMENTAL RIGHT

The right to privacy and data protection are two different rights but their evolution is closely interlinked. The right to respect private life appeared for the first time in 1948 with the Universal Declaration of Human rights (UDHR)⁵⁸ and two years later in the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR)⁵⁹.

The legal formulation on the concept of privacy is broadly attributed to the work of the American lawyers Samuel Warren and Louis Brandeis in 1890.⁶⁰ In Europe, the typification of a right to privacy is often claimed to appear as a reaction to the abuses of totalitarian states before and during the WWII, thus, as a vertical and negative freedom for citizens against the interferences by the State.

The computerization of society in the 60's and 70's, particularly in the United States, led to the development of a new conceptualization of the right under the notion of informational privacy.⁶¹ Based on the US pioneering work, the 1970's turned into a fertile ground for European legislation on how public authorities and private entities dealt with data and computers. Through the years, the expansion of concept has led several authors to develop theoretical frameworks to explain what actually privacy is.⁶²

The German federal Land of Hessen was the first to pass European legislation on data protection (Datenschutz). Not much later, national laws of Sweden (1973), Germany (1977), and France (1978) would follow it, establishing the foundries of what later became EU's right data protection⁶³. In order to harmonize the blossoming number of national laws, the 80's contemplated several supranational and international attempts to shape and control data protection. Of particular interest is the adoption of Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) guidelines in 1980⁶⁴, followed by the Council of Europe convention on automated processing in 1981(Convention 108)⁶⁵.

⁵⁸ United Nations (UN), Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 10 December 1948; Available at <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights> .(Last accessed 22 March 2022)

⁵⁹ Council of Europe, European Convention on Human Rights, CETS No. 005, 1950. Available at https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf. (Last accessed 22 March 2022).

⁶⁰ Samuel D. Warren & Louis D. Brandeis, The Right to Privacy, in Harvard Law Review, 1890, Vol. 4, No. 5, p 193-220.

⁶¹ Alan F. Westin, Privacy And Freedom, 25 Wash. & Lee L. Rev. 166 (1968). Available at: <https://scholarlycommons.law.wlu.edu/wlulr/vol25/iss1/20>

⁶² See Alan Westin's Four Privacy States, Roger Clarke's Classification, Anita Allen's "Unpopular Privacy," Finn, Wright, and Friedewald's Types of Privacy and Solove's categorisation of privacy theories. More recently, Bert Jaap Koops synthesised the theoretical production into his "typology of privacy." The two-dimensional model that consists of eight basic types of privacy (1. bodily, 2. intellectual, 3. spatial, 4. decisional, 5. communicational, 6. associational, 7. proprietary, and 8. behavioral privacy), with an overlay of a ninth type (9. informational privacy) overlapping, but not coinciding, with the former eight basic types. Bert-Jaap Koops et al., «A Typology of Privacy», SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 24 March 2016), <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2754043>

⁶³ G. González Fuster, 'The Beginning of EU Data Protection', in *The Emergence of Personal Data Protection as a Fundamental Right of the EU*, ed. Gloria González Fuster, Law, Governance and Technology Series (Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2014), 111–62, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05023-2_5.

⁶⁴ OECD, 1980 Guidelines Governing the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data. An updated version was adopted in 2013. Available at <https://www.oecd.org/sti/ieconomy/oecdguidelinesonthe protectionofprivacyandtransborderflowsofpersonaldata.htm> (Last accessed on 21 March 2022).

⁶⁵ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS

Soon after the Treaty on the European Union was adopted in October 1995⁶⁶, the European Parliament and the Council passed the Directive 95/46/EC on Data Protection⁶⁷. The Directive had per objective the harmonisation and protection of fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons in respect of processing activities and to ensure the free flow of personal data between member states.

Through the years, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) case law has discussed, shaped, and clarified many aspects involving data protection. Notably, under the checks and balance formula in article 52(1) the Court has consistently defended that the respect for private life is not an absolute right, but that instead, needs balancing among other competing rights and interests. At the same time, the Court has clarified that the ECHR does not only prohibit interfering with rights, but, in certain circumstances, also actively acts to protect them.

At the EU level, the adoption of the EU Charter in 2000, consecrated in its article 8, the right to data protection as an autonomous fundamental right. In this regard, it should be noted that the notion of fundamental rights is a genuine legal construct of the EU. The founding treaties of the European Communities did not have any reference to them. Originally, human rights, as they were understood in the United Nations or Council of Europe framework were regarded as a strange body to the economic integration and internal market. Today fundamental rights are claimed to be a defining element of the EU evolution into an international organization with its own and unitary legal system.⁶⁸ In its permanent evolution, the Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU) continues to clarify the scope and normative role of data protection a fundamental right.

The overlapping scopes between the fundamental rights to privacy and the right to data protection are still a matter of debate today. The blurriness of their respective limits has enabled some positions to defend the autonomous character of data protection and others to understand it as an integral part of privacy.⁶⁹

3.2 COUNCIL OF EUROPE AND DATA PROTECTION

3.2.1 THE EUROPEAN CONVENTION ON HUMAN RIGHTS, ARTICLE 8

At the level of the Council of Europe, the right to personal data, protection falls under the scope of article 8 of the ECHR, which guarantees the right to respect for private and family life, home, and correspondence.

<p>Right to respect for private and family life, home and correspondence</p> <p>Article 8 of the ECHR</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her. 2. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified. 3. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.
---	--

Paragraph 2 of article 8 lays down those cases when restrictions to the right are permitted. This is the case when an interference with the right occurs “in accordance with the law and is necessary for a democratic society in the interests of national security, public safety or the economic well-being of the

No. 08, 28 January 1981 (“Convention 108”), see <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/108> (last accessed on 21 March 2022). Also see TeNDER, p. 43.

⁶⁶ Treaty on the European Union

⁶⁷ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and the free flow of such data.

⁶⁸ P. P. Craig and G. De Búrca, eds., *The Evolution of EU Law*, 2nd ed (Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 2011).

⁶⁹ S. Rodotà, ‘Data Protection as a Fundamental Right’, in *Reinventing Data Protection?*, ed. Serge Gutwirth et al. (Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2009), 77–82, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9498-9_3.

country, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others (Article 8(2) ECHR).

3.2.2 CONVENTION 108 AND THE MODERNISED CONVENTION 108+

The Convention 108 of 28 January 1981 is the first legally binding international instrument in the data protection field. All forty-seven countries of the Council of Europe are parties. It applies to data processing conducted by both the private and public sectors, including data processing by the judiciary branch and law enforcement authorities.⁷⁰

The Convention 108 is not subject to the judicial supervision of the ECtHR but has been taken into consideration in the case law of the ECtHR within the context of Article 8 of the ECHR⁷¹.

In 2018, the Convention was modernised (Convention 108+)⁷² to respond to the new challenges of the digital era, the globalisation of processing operations, and to allow safer exchanges of personal data.⁷³

3.3 EUROPEAN UNION DATA PROTECTION LAW

EU law is composed by primary law (treaties) and secondary law (Regulations, Directives, and Decisions). The EU constitutional provisions on data protection are provided under the Charter of Fundamental Rights (Charter)⁷⁴ and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)⁷⁵.

3.3.1 PRIMARY LAW

The TFEU also known as the treaty of Lisbon, entered into force in 2009 it recognized for the first time that EU policies impacted EU citizens' rights which led to the approval of the Charter of Fundamental Rights in 2000. The text only became legally binding in 2009 as primary law, with the entry into force of the TFEU, and it in its article 16 grants the competence to the EU in order to legislate on data protection matters.⁷⁶

Article 8 of the Charter establishes the right to protect personal data as a separate from the right for respect to private and family life (Article 7 of the Charter):

Article 8 of the Charter	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. <i>Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.</i>2. <i>Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified.</i>3. <i>Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.</i>
--------------------------	---

Under the EU law, fundamental rights are not absolute, this means that they can be interfered or limited provided if certain conditions are observed. Following the balancing formula set by the ECHR, Article 52(1) of the Charter identifies the conditions under which the right may be limited, namely when:

⁷⁰ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law.

⁷¹ ECtHR, *Zv. Finland*, N° 22009/93, 22 February 1997.

⁷² <https://rm.coe.int/convention-108-convention-for-the-protection-of-individuals-with-regar/16808b36f1>, accessed 21 March 2022.

⁷³ CoE Data protection leaflet, <https://rm.coe.int/leaflet-data-protection-final-26-april-2019/1680943556>, accessed 21 March 2022.

⁷⁴ European Parliament, Council and Commission, Charter on Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 7 December 2000 ("Charter"), see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT> (last accessed on 17 February 2022)

⁷⁵ EU, Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, 25 March 1957 (and as amended) ("TFEU"), see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:12016ME/TXT> (last accessed on 14 February 2022).

⁷⁶ *ibid*

- i. It is provided for in law,
- ii. Respects the essence of those rights and freedoms,
- iii. It is proportional and necessary, and
- iv. Meets the objective of general interests recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others.

The connection between the Council of Europe and the EU interpretation of the rights is set in Article 52(3) of the Charter, which establishes that when the Charter contains an equivalent right in the ECHR, “the meaning and scope of those rights shall be the same as those laid down by the said Convention.”⁷⁷

3.3.2 SECONDARY LAW

3.3.2.1 EU: The General Data protection regulation

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the main legal instrument governing the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of their personal data and the free flow of such data. The GDPR became fully enforceable in the European Union in May 2018 in replacement of Directive 95/46/EC.⁷⁸

The GDPR applies to the “processing of personal data wholly or partly by automated means and to the processing other than by automated means of personal data which form part of a filing system”.⁷⁹ It applies to processing activities carried out by individuals, companies, or organizations of personal data relating to individuals in the EU. Based on the principle of extraterritoriality, the GDPR applies to the data of EU residents regardless of whether or not the data processing takes place in the EU (Article 3(2) of the GDPR). Importantly, the regulation only covers the processing of personal data, this means that it does not apply to non-personal data or to the processing of personal data of deceased persons or of legal entities nor to data not considered as personal. Also, under the household exemption, its provisions do not apply to data processing by an individual for purely personal reasons or for activities carried out in one’s home provided there is no connection to a professional or commercial activity.

Differently from Directives, Regulations are legal instruments directly applicable to all Member States, however, as indicated in recital 10, the GDPR still needs to be transposed into the national laws, thus offering a certain margin of discretion.⁸⁰ This means that Member States might for instance subject certain aspects of a processing activities to stricter rules in their national laws than those foreseen in the GDPR.⁸¹ This is the case of the processing of health data where further national conditions might exist, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health.⁸²

⁷⁷ EU Charter article 52: “Any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others. [...]3. In so far as this Charter contains rights that correspond to rights guaranteed by the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the meaning, and scope of those rights shall be the same as those laid down by the said Convention. This provision shall not prevent Union law from providing more extensive protection.”

⁷⁸ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (“EU Directive 95/46/EC”), see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31995L0046> (last accessed on 6 March 2022).

⁷⁹ Article 2(1) of the GDPR.

⁸⁰ Recital 10 of the GDPR. See also European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law,

⁸¹ Art 9(4) of the GDPR means that harmonisation in the area of health data will be limited. In the specific case of genetic data, biometric data, or data concerning health, article 9(4) of the GDPR contemplates the possibility that the Member States maintain or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to their processing. Also Member States can introduce derogations in the context of processing activities for scientific or historical purposes from data subjects’ rights (Article 89 of the GDPR).

⁸² Article 9(4) of the GDPR

3.3.2.2 Guidelines and authorities:

In addition to law, an important source of guidance when implementing data protection law are the opinions and recommendations of the EU independent bodies; the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), and the European Data Protection Board (EDPB).

The EDPS is the EU's independent data protection authority, entrusted with three main roles: i) supervision of the processing of personal data by EU Institutions and bodies; ii) advisory role for those entities on data protection matters, and iii) monitoring role with regards to new technologies involving data protection issues⁸³.

Meanwhile the EDPB is established by the GDPR as “an independent European body, which contributes to the consistent application of data protection rules throughout the European Union and promotes cooperation between the EU’s data protection authorities.”⁸⁴

The following opinions, guidelines, and codes issued by the EDPS and EDPB are relevant to the MES-CoBraD research.

Table 4 MES-CoBraD institutional guidelines and opinions on data protection

Opinions	
EDPS, 2020	A Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research, Adopted on 6 January 2020
EDPB, 2021	Response to the request from the European Commission for clarifications on the consistent application of the GDPR, focusing on health research, Adopted on 2 February 2021
EC, Green paper SWD (2014)	European Commission Green Paper on mobile Health ("mHealth"), Adopted on 10 April 2014.
EDPB, 3/2019	EDPB Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR), Adopted on 23 January 2019.
Guidelines	
EDPB 04/2019,	EDPB Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default Adopted on 13 November 2019
EDPB, 1/2019	EDPB Guidelines 1/2019 on Codes of Conduct and Monitoring Bodies under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 12 February 2019
EDPB, 03/2020	EDPB Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak, Adopted on 21 April 2020
EDPB, 07/2020	EDPB Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, Adopted on 07 July 2021.
EDPB 01/2021	EDPB Guidelines 01/2021 on Examples regarding Data Breach Notification, Adopted on 19 January 2021.
EDPB 10/2020	EDPB Guidelines 10/2020 on restrictions under Article 23 GDPR, Adopted on 13

⁸³ EDPS, About (website), see https://edps.europa.eu/about-edps_en (last accessed on 20 February 2022).

⁸⁴ Since the entry into force of the GDPR in 2018, the EDPB has replaced the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. EDPB, About EDPB (website), see https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb_en (last accessed on 20 February 2022).

	October 2021.
EDPB 05/2020	EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 4 May 2020.
WP251	Article 29 Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on October 2017, Endorsed by the EDPB.
WP259	Article WP29 Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 28 November 2017. Endorsed by the EDPB.
EDPB-EDPS, 5/2021	EDPB-EDPS Joint Opinion 5/2021 on the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act). Adopted on 18 June 2021
AEPD-EDPS	10 misunderstandings related to anonymisation, Adopted on 27 April 2021
EDPB 3/2019	EDPB Opinion 3/2019 concerning the Questions and Answers on the interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR), Adopted on 23 January 2019
Recommendations	
Recommendation No. R (97)	Council of Europe, Committee of Ministers, Recommendation No. R (97) 5 on the Protection of Medical Data. Adopted on 13 February 1997.
CM/Rec(2019)2	Council of Europe Recommendation CM/Rec (2019)2 of the Committee of Ministers to member States on the protection of health-related data, Adopted on 27 March 2019
EDBP, R01/2020	Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data (Version 2.0), Adopted on 18 June 2021

3.4 MEMBER STATES AND THIRD COUNTRIES DATA PROTECTION NORMATIVE FRAMEWORKS

Member States might establish derogations to the provisions in the GDPR by “determining more precisely specific requirements for the processing and other measures to ensure lawful and fair processing”.⁸⁵ As a result, it is necessary to take into account the particularities of applicable national laws in the different MES-CoBraD pilot sites. The following subsection offers a brief summary of the relevant national legal frameworks involved in the project.

3.4.1 SPAIN

The Spanish implementation of the data protection regime is found in the Organic Law 3/2018 on the Protection of Personal Data and the Guarantee of Digital Rights (the Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de Protección de Datos y Garantía de los Derechos Digitales), which entered into force on December 2018 ⁸⁶.

Regarding the processing of health data in the context of scientific research, a specific framework is developed in the “Additional Provision 17th (1) (2) of the same Organic Law 3/2018. Derogations to the processing of personal data can be found in sections c) , d) , f) and g), conditioned to the adoption of safeguards and the adoption of technical and organisational measures:

⁸⁵ Article 9(4), GDPR.

⁸⁶ See <https://delajusticia.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Ley-proteccion-datos.pdf> (last accessed on 16 February 2022). Also see Bird&Bird, GDPR Tracker (Spain) (“GDPR Tracker Spain”)

In addition, the Catalan Code of Conduct for the processing of personal data in the health sector ⁸⁷, applies as far as the MES-CoBraD partner is located in that territory. The code aims to create a common framework and unify the criteria in the implementation of data protection rules in the health sector. It establishes the measures and procedures to be followed by the controller and processors in the field of medical assistance and research activities (Article 112-1).

The data protection supervisory authority in Spain is Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEPD)⁸⁸. Autonomous territories also have their own supervisory authorities, as is the case of the Catalan Authority of Data Protection.⁸⁹

3.4.2 ITALY

The Italian implementation of the data protection regime is found in the Legislative Decree no. 101 of 10 August 2018 ("The Decree") and which entered into force in September 2018 ⁹⁰. There are a number of derogations from the GDPR included in the relevant Italian law, including with respect to processing of special categories of data ⁹¹. With regards to health data the Italian law in its article 2-septies (m) provides that the processing of genetic, biometric, and health data shall be carried out only if both the processing complies with Article 9(2) GDPR and certain security measures, such as encryption, pseudonymisation, and minimisation are implemented. The decree further allows personal data to be processed, stored, and transferred to another controller after the normal period for processing and even after the termination of the main processing if carried out for scientific, historical, or statistical purposes as well as archiving in the public interest. Guidance will be issued for the processing of personal data for this purpose, aiming to identify adequate guarantees for the rights and freedoms of the data subject in accordance with Article 89 GDPR ⁹².

The Data Protection Authority in Italy is the Garante per la protezione dei dati personali ⁹³.

Further guidance on the security measures on the processing of special categories of data will be to be indicated by the Garante every two years. Since the GDPR, the Garante has not adopted new safeguards. Until now, the Garante has updated the General Authorisation No. 8/2016 on processing of genetic data (section 5.7) and issued further several guidelines and opinions on the processing of data concerning health, biometric and genetic data.⁹⁴

⁸⁷ Codi de Conducta per al tractament de dades personals en l'àmbit sanitari last accessed 15/02/2022 https://apdcat.gencat.cat/web/.content/02-drets_i_obligacions/documents/5535CODI_DE_CONDUCTA_AMBIT_SANITARI_CSC_v.2.pdf

⁸⁸ Agencia Española Protección de Datos <https://www.aepd.es/es> (last accessed on 16 February 2022).

⁸⁹ Autoritat Catalana Proteccio de Dades <https://apdcat.gencat.cat/en/inici/index.html> (last accessed on 16 February 2022).

⁹⁰ The Decree did not repeal the Italian Data Protection Act but rather amended any provisions of the act conflicting with the GDPR .See Bird&Bird, GDPR Tracker (Italy) ("GDPR Tracker Italy") <https://www.twobirds.com/en/capabilities/practices/privacy-and-data-protection/general-data-protection-regulation/gdpr-tracker/italy>

⁹¹ GDPR Tracker Italy.

⁹²ibid.

⁹³ Garante ; <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/> (last accessed on 16 February 2022).

⁹⁴ IDPA, General Application Order Concerning Biometrics as of November, 2014, see <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/3590114> (last accessed on 16 February 2022); IDPA, Guidelines on Processing Personal Data to Perform Customer Satisfaction Surveys in Healthcare Sector as of May 5, 2011, see <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/3853781> (last accessed on 16 February 2022); IDPA, Authorization №2/2014 Concerning Processing of Data Suitable for Disclosing Health or Sex Life as of December 30, 2014, see <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/3800455> (last accessed on 16 February 2022); IDPA, Guidelines on the Electronic Health Record and the Health File as of July 16, 2009, see <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/1672821> (last accessed on 16 February 2022); IDPA, General Authorization №8/2012 for the Processing of Genetic Data as of December 13, 2012, see <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/2474250> (last accessed on 16 February 2022).

3.4.3 GREECE

In Greece, the national implementation of the GDPR, the Greek Data Protection Act (Greek DPA)⁹⁵, applies to the processing of healthcare data, with important foundations for the processing of personal data in the context of healthcare and medical research in the Code of Medical Ethics.⁹⁶ The Code describes the patients' right to receive all necessary information regarding their health status as well as their right not to know.

All patients' personal data are protected under the obligation of Medical confidentiality, and those which must be processed for health-related purposes such as the age, sex, address, and medical history of patients are extensively described in the Code.

The processing of health-related data for scientific research purposes is permitted under the condition of existing safeguards, including DPO appointment, encryption of data, and restriction on data by data controllers and processors and requires the data subject's explicit consent.

As an exemption to the general rule of informed consent, Art. 9(1) GDPR, the data controller may further process Health data for research purposes if the controller can prove its competing interest in processing such data against the interest of the data subjects in not having their data processed. In the latter case, the data controller must take appropriate and specific measures (Art. 30(1) Law 4624/ 2019)⁹⁷. This appears as the only possibility for an exemption to process special data categories based on other legal grounds than consent for scientific research purposes. In all cases, the research carried by the partner must be approved by the competent scientific council and the bioethics committee (Art. 24(2)(d) Law 3418/2005 and Art. 23 Law 4521/2018)⁹⁸.

The Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPa) is a constitutionally consolidated independent Authority ⁹⁹.

3.4.4 SWEDEN

The Sweden's Personal Data Act (1998:204) was repealed in May 2018 and replaced by the Swedish Data Protection Act (2018:218) and the Swedish Data Protection Regulation (2018:219) to govern alongside the EU's GDPR.¹⁰⁰

The data privacy legislation regulates data protection principles, the legal bases for processing personal data, rules around special category data, and transparency requirements.

The Personal Data Act paragraph 3(7) indicates that sensitive personal data can be processed according to the GDPR Art. 9(2)(j) if the processing is necessary for statistical purposes and the public interest, for the statistics project for which the processing takes place, clearly outweighs the risk for unfair infringement of the individuals' integrity that the processing may cause.¹⁰¹ There is specific legislation

⁹⁵ Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPa), measures for implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data, and transposition of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, and other provisions, Law 4624/2019 (Government Gazette, Series A, Issue N 137, p. 3379). www.opengov.gr/ministryofjustice/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2018/02/sxedio_nomou_prostasia_pd.pdf (in Greek) (last accessed on 16 February 2022).

⁹⁶ Code of Medical Deontology, Law 3418/2005 (Government Gazette, Series A, Issue N. 287, p. 5391).

⁹⁷ Law No. 4624 Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDPa), measures for implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data, and transposition of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, and other provisions. https://www.dpa.gr/sites/default/files/2020/08/LAW%204624_2019_EN_TRANSLATED%20BY%20THE%20HDPa.PDF (Last accessed 7 March 2022).

⁹⁸ Supra

⁹⁹ <http://www.dpa.gr>

¹⁰⁰ See Bird&Bird, GDPR Tracker (Italy) ("GDPR Tracker Sweden")

¹⁰¹ GDPR Tracker Sweden

with regards to patient data, the Patient Data Act (2008:355) which provides further conditions for the processing of personal data in health care.¹⁰²

3.4.5 THIRD COUNTRIES

3.4.5.1 UK

The UK's data protection framework is currently regulated by the Data Protection Act 2018, which incorporates the EU GDPR and supplements its provisions. The Data Protection Act 2018 focuses significantly on data subject rights, "special category" personal data, data protection fees, data protection offenses, consent from children, and enforcement. While the UK is no longer be an EU member state as of March 29, 2019, to this day there has been no update with regard to its existing data privacy laws.

Furthermore, as a signatory to the Convention 108 of the Council of Europe, the exception provided for in Article 2(8)(1) of the aforementioned regulations, which allows cross-border transfers, would continue to apply to the UK.¹⁰³

The Medical Research Council is responsible for co-coordinating and funding medical research in the UK. With regards to the legal basis for processing special categories of data, it has advised against the use of consent as an adequate legal basis arguing¹⁰⁴ that the 'GDPR's consent requirements do not often apply to research.¹⁰⁵

3.4.5.2 Israel

Data protection in Israel is governed primarily by the Protection of Privacy Law, 5741-1981 ('the Privacy Law')¹⁰⁶ and the Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty, 5752-1992¹⁰⁷. The latter sets out the fundamental rights of privacy whereas the former focuses on the protection of personal data and information.¹⁰⁸

Guidelines on data protection issues are provided by the Israeli regulator, the Privacy Protection Authority ('PPA') (formerly known as the Israel Law, Information, and Technology Authority ("ILITA"))¹⁰⁹. With regards to data referring to a patient's physical or mental health, or data about his\her medical treatment. Not defined in the Privacy Law, but in the Patient's Rights Law, 5756-1996.¹¹⁰

Privacy protection regulation for the transfer of personal information to Databases outside the State Borders, 5761-2001 set out the conditions for data retention and use applying to a database located in Israel (section 2(4) of the Regulation).

¹⁰² Patient Data Act 2008, <https://www.datainspektionen.se/other-lang/in-english/the-patient-data-act/>

¹⁰³ See Opinion regarding the continuation of cross-border transfers of personal data, from Israeli based organizations to UK based organizations post Brexit, available at https://www.gov.il/en/departments/publications/reports/gb_personaldata (Last accessed 18 January 2022)

¹⁰⁴ This is supported by the UK Medical Research Council, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): Consent in Research and Confidentiality: Guidance Note 3 (March 2018, updated May 2018).

¹⁰⁵ UK Medical Research Council, GDPR and Data Protection Act 2018: Key Facts for Research (13 June 2018), available at <https://mrc.ukri.org/documents/pdf/gdpr-key-facts-for-research/>,

¹⁰⁶ Protection of Privacy Law, 5741-1981- unofficial translation available <https://www.gov.il/BlobFolder/legalinfo/legislation/en/ProtectionofPrivacyLaw57411981unofficialtranslatio.pdf>, (last accessed 21 March 2022)

¹⁰⁷ Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty, 5752-1992, <https://platform.dataguidance.com/legal-research/basic-law-human-dignity-and-liberty-5752-1992> (last accessed 21 March 2022)

¹⁰⁸ See ICLG, Digital health laws and regulations 2022, available <https://iclg.com/practice-areas/digital-health-laws-and-regulations/israel>, (last accessed 21 March 2022)

¹⁰⁹ Privacy Protection Authority, available https://www.gov.il/he/Departments/the_privacy_protection_authority, (last accessed 21 March 2022)

¹¹⁰ Available in Hebrew: https://www.health.gov.il/LegislationLibrary/Zchuyot_01.pdf (last accessed 21 March 2022)

4 CAPITA SELECTA: DATA PROTECTION AND MES-COBRA D

4.1 PERSONAL DATA AND HEALTH DATA

In EU and European data protection law, only personal data is subject to data protection rules. Therefore, as a preliminary step to determine the legal obligations and responsibilities of the consortium towards data protection, it is necessary to first identify which types of data are being processed.

4.1.1 WHAT IS PERSONAL DATA?

Personal data Article 4(1) of the GDPR Recital 30 of the GDPR	Personal data ¹ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person;
--	--

The definition of personal data starts in a vague fashion, its reference to “any information” allows to associate it with every meaning or significance.¹¹¹ In practice, a piece of information contains “personal data” if an individual is identified directly by the information or is indirectly identifiable using additional information. The definition of personal data purportedly appears to be broad, flexible, and adaptable to technological context.¹¹²

The opposite of personal data is anonymous data. Provided that anonymous data is not subject to data Protection law, the identification of one or the other, represents an integral aspect of the controller’s evaluation of its data protection responsibilities. Such exercise should be carried by the controller “at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself” in order for the controller to adopt appropriate measures and safeguards to protect data protection principles and data subject rights.¹¹³

Formally speaking, the medium how personal data is stored or how it is used is not relevant to the applicability of data protection law. Analogue, digital, images, sound files, or cell samples will be considered personal data, as long as the data relates to the individual.¹¹⁴

4.1.2 WHEN IS A DATA SUBJECT CONSIDERED TO BE IDENTIFIED OR IDENTIFIABLE?

The test of reasonable likelihood of identification Recital 26 of the GDPR	To ascertain whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the 1) means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, 2) by the controller or another person to identify the natural person 3) directly or indirectly. To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used, account should be taken of 4) all objective factors, such as i) the costs of and ii) the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration iii) the available technology at the time of the processing and iv) technological developments.
---	---

In order to assess “identifiability, Recital 26 of the GDPR introduces a test of a reasonable likelihood of identification. The test must contemplate the means “likely to be used” not only by the partners in the

¹¹¹ Similarly the modernised Convention 108 in its article 2 (a) defines personal data as “ any information relating to an identified or identifiable individual ("data subject") .

¹¹² Nadezhda Purtova, ‘The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law,’ Law, Innovation, and Technology 10(1) (2018): See also WP29 Opinion 4/2007 on the concept of personal data, p.4

¹¹³ See guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.

¹¹⁴ The case of cell samples is specifically dealt in Article 4 (13) of the GDPR as information that relates to the “individual’s inherited or acquired genetic characteristics, provide unique information about their health or physiology and result from an analysis of a biological sample of this person”

consortium but for “any other person” to break the anonymisation.

As expressed, it is sufficient that the person concerned is potentially identifiable. The EDPB adopts a broad understanding of what ‘identified or identifiable’ means. In their view, “identified” refers to a person who is known, or distinguished in a group, and “identifiable” is a person who is not identified yet, but identification is possible.¹¹⁵ There is no need for actual identification of the data subject or an intention to identify.

Moreover, it is not even necessary that the data is held by the same person processing the “information”¹¹⁶. This means for instance that when the identification is only (theoretically) possible to the controller but not the processor, the processing activities performed by the processor are still considered to be on personal data.

Regarding the concept “of means,” the GDPR includes relative values concerning costs and time. It is also important to note that the assessment has a future-oriented nature and thus must be periodically conducted to embrace technological developments. For this reason, when considering whether we are discussing about the existence of personal data or not, a “tailored, context- specific” analysis is required.¹¹⁷

In the context of MES-CoBraD, if the consortium wished to rely on anonymisation a test of likelihood would need to be carried and its result adequately justified.

4.1.3 SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA

There are special categories of personal data that are considered particularly sensitive in relation to the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects. Its processing is deemed riskier and thus worth of an enhanced protection.¹¹⁸ As a matter of fact, the processing of special categories of data is a priori forbidden, and there is only a limited number of cases where its processing is lawful. The processing of data relating to medical diagnosis, scientific research is one of those cases.¹¹⁹

Within the GDPR (Article 9), the following categories are considered special categories of data:

- i. personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin;
- ii. personal data revealing political opinions, religious or other beliefs, including philosophical beliefs;
- iii. personal data revealing trade union membership;
- iv. genetic data and biometric data processed for the purpose of identifying a person;
- v. personal data concerning health, sexual life, or sexual orientation.

Special attention should be given to categories of data that do not fall under the generic definition of personal data mentioned above but to a specific group of special types of data.

4.1.4 DATA CONCERNING HEALTH

Data concerning health Article 4(15) of the	'data concerning health' means personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status;
---	--

¹¹⁵ EDPB, 21 April 2020, Guidelines 04/2020 on the use of location data and contact tracing tools in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak; See also EDPB, 15 December 2020, Response to Professor Dr. Katja Becker regarding the impacts of the GDPR on Research

¹¹⁶ Ibid. In this respect the CJEU has clarified that, it is not required that all information identifying the data subject be in the hands of a single person See CJEU, 19 October 2016, judgment Breyer, C-582/14, point 43.

¹¹⁷ N. Purtova, 'The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law,' Law, Innovation, and Technology 10(1) (2018).

¹¹⁸ Recital 51 of the GDPR

¹¹⁹ See article 9 (2) of the GDPR.

GDPR See also recital 35	
-----------------------------	--

Health data includes all data pertaining to the health status of a data subject, which reveals information relating to the past, current or future physical or mental health status of the data subject.¹²⁰ Examples of health data are:

- i. Information about the natural person collected in the course of the registration for, or the provision of, health care services as referred to in Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council to that natural person;
- ii. A number, symbol, or particular assigned to a natural person to uniquely identify the natural person for health purposes;
- iii. Information derived from the testing or examination of a body part or bodily substance, including from genetic data and biological samples;
- iv. Any information on, for example, a disease, disability, disease risk, medical history, clinical treatment, or the physiological or biomedical state of the data subject independent of its source, for example from a physician or other health professional, a hospital, a medical device, or an in vitro diagnostic test.

Health data is considered a special category of data, and as such, its processing is a priori forbidden. Member States are allowed to keep or introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data, or data concerning health. See below section on Member States derogations.

4.1.5 WHAT DATA IS PROCESSED DURING THE PROJECT MES-COBRA D

The project MES-CoBraD uses existing and prospective RWD concerning health to populate the MES-CoBraD platform and train the predictive algorithms, based on the criteria of identifiability might either be:¹²¹

- Non-personal data: when the information cannot be used to identify a natural person. In that case, the information is not affected by data protection rules.
- Personal data: data that can directly or indirectly identify a natural person. The data protection rules apply., MES-CoBraD might process two types of personal data:
 - a. Non-sensitive data (Article 4 (1) of the GDPR)
 - b. Special category of personal data (Article 9 of the GDPR).

The categories of RWD are exhaustively listed and described in the MES-CoBraD Project Manual.¹²² At the time of submission of this second version of the DMP (November 2021) seven RWD sources of data have been identified in MES-CoBraD. ¹²³

Table 5 MES-CoBraD Research Datasets based on D3.2 Project Manual V2

Data Set ID	Description
DS_01	Clinical symptoms & history

¹²⁰ Recital 35 of the GDPR

¹²¹ Article 4(1) of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679

¹²² MES- CoBraD D3.2 Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation – v2, September 2021.

¹²³ For further information on the RWD description, please check v2 of the MES-CoBraD Project Manual (p.26) and the Data Management Plan (D2.2)

DS_02	Physical Examination and Neuropsychological Testing
DS_03	Biological samples
DS_04	Physiology
DS_05	Medical Device data
DS_06	Wearables

The MES-CoBraD platform incorporates a de-personalisation module configurable according to each type of RWD.¹²⁴ The data outcome from the module might either be fully anonymised data or pseudonymised data.

If a dataset is successfully anonymised at the de-personalisation module, the data uploaded will no longer be personal data and as a result, no processing of personal data will take place at the MES-CoBraD platform. Alternatively, if the data remains capable of identifying the data subject the data at the platform will continue to be considered personal data, and as a result the data protection framework will continue to apply.

A follow-up assessment on the diverse types and sources of data processed at the MES-CoBraD platform will be elaborated during the project and presented at the updated version of this deliverable.

4.2 DATA PROCESSING ACTIVITIES IN MES-COBRA D

The following section examines the concept of data processing, in order to offer a description of the envisaged processing activities during the project.

At the stage of writing, there are still technical and contextual elements that remain undefined and will need to be followed up by the project prior to any processing activity at the platform takes place.

4.2.1 THE DATA PROCESSING LIFECYCLE IN MES-COBRA D

Describing the processing activities in MES-CoBraD requires a first identification of the datasets processing lifecycles. In MES-CoBraD, both for retrospective and prospective data the processing lifecycle begins at the moment of collection of the personal data.

The lifecycle of the processing of data collected and stored by the medical partners for healthcare purposes as well as medical research different project than MES-CoBraD, fall under the individual controllership of the medical partner and will not be assessed in this document.

4.2.2 DEFINING A DATA PROCESSING ACTIVITY

Processing- Article 4(2) of the GDPR ¹²⁵	'processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction;
---	--

Data processing refers to any operation on personal data using automated means (i.e., computers, mobile devices) as well as manual ones, when the personal data is contained or aimed to be contained in a file

¹²⁴ MES-CoBraD, D5.1 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – v1, March 2022

¹²⁵ The concept is shared in the and the Modernised Convention 108, Art. 2 (b).

¹²⁶. In practice, the processing of data might group different activities or operations that precede and follow one another. From collecting the data until it is destroyed, the data can be used in many different ways.

4.2.3 THE DATA PROCESSING ACTIVITIES IN MES-COBRA D

The following list identifies and briefly describes the processing activities envisaged during the MES-CoBraD Project.

Table 6 MES-CoBraD Data processing activities

	Data processing activity	Relevant MES-CoBraD
1.	<p>Data collection process for storage and further processing: Include the collection of personal data from former studies, sample collection, questionnaires, web forms, paper forms, interviews, direct observation, social networks, sensor capture, digital recording.</p> <p>Before the collection stage, medical partners, and the medical professionals will have informed the patients/participants about their participation in the MES-CoBraD research, and to that end, provide to them all the necessary information.</p>	Data collection component (WP3, D3.2 WP5, D5.1, WP7 D7.1)
2.	<p>Alteration/ Preparation: Depending on the type of RWD, the medical partner will prepare the data set for its processing at the MES-CoBraD platform. This can involve a preliminary preparation of data and the data harmonisation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preliminary preparation of data: preliminary operations on data aimed to facilitate its further processing, including the digitalisation of handwriting notes, the use of statistical models or mathematical operations on the data. - Data harmonisation: steps applied to the RWD including 1. Data curation; 2. Metadata extraction; 3. Data model identification; 4. Data integration, standardisation, transformation of data into a cohesive data set. 	Data harmonisation component (WP5, D5.1)
3.	De-personalisation: The implementation of anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques, such as: hashing, encryption, aggregation, adding noise, removing variables /categories.	De-personalisation component WP5, D5.1
4.	<p>Storage: The storage of personal data means those operations aimed at the organization, structuring, storage, preservation, including backups via any media, including: physical servers, virtual clouds, LAN or WAN, hard drive, external devices.</p> <p>Once data has been through the de-personalisation module, scientists and clinicians must verify whether the data can be uploaded within the platform to make it available to other components and users. If adequate, the data is then uploaded and stored into the data lake.</p> <p>The personal data processed in MES-CoBraD is stored at the data lake, a cloud</p>	Data lake WP5, D5.

¹²⁶ In its recital 15 the GDPR defines file as “any structured set of personal data accessible according to determined criteria, whether this set is centralized, decentralized or distributed functionally or geographically”. The files or sets of files not structured according to specific criteria, do not fall within the scope of the Regulation

	solution with the ability to store different types of data in a tailored manner. ¹²⁷ The system shall store the RWD collected by the Medical partners as well as the outputs of the platform.	
5.	Exploitation: Consultation by different partners developing the platform including the training of AI algorithms. ¹²⁸	WP5, D5.1
6.	International transfer: data transfers when it includes transfer to a third countries outside the EU.	Not applicable
7.	Destruction: deleting, erasing of data that may be contained in Systems or files, so that it cannot be recovered from storage media.	Data storage. WP2, D2.2; WP5, D5.1

The list of data processing activities and its description will be monitored and completed during the course of the project and reported in the updated version of this deliverable.

4.3 DE-PERSONALISATION OF PERSONAL DATA

This section elaborates on the notions of anonymization and pseudonymization under the GDPR and its relation to the research in MES-CoBraD. First, it offers a theoretical introduction to the concepts of anonymization and pseudonymisation. Second, it assesses the de-personalisation module envisaged for the MES-CoBraD platform and draws preliminary recommendations based on which are, at the stage of writing, the legal implications of the expected processing activities.

4.3.1 WHAT DOES ANONYMISATION MEAN?

Under data protection law, anonymisation is a processing activity that concludes with the elimination of all identifying elements from a set of personal data so that the data subject cannot be identifiable. This means that for data to be anonymous, no element may be left in information which could be, by exercising reasonable effort, serve to re-identify the person(s) from which a piece of data is originally related. When data have been successfully anonymised, they are no longer personal data, and data protection legislation no longer applies.

Once the technique/combination of techniques has been applied, the anonymization process should make any processing of personal data impossible. The EDPB explains that data "only loses its qualification as personal data if the anonymity is absolute and no longer any means reasonably likely to be implemented allows us to go back to break anonymity".¹²⁹

Anonymised data should not be confused with pseudonymised data. Pseudonymised data is still personal data and thus subject to data protection law.¹³⁰ It is important to understand that in data protection, the meaning of what is personal and anonymous might differ from what is commonly understood in other areas of knowledge. What matters is whether certain data might refer to an identified or identifiable data subject.

4.3.2 ANONYMISATION TECHNIQUES

There is no one single anonymisation formula applicable to all cases. This means that finding an optimal technique or combination of techniques for the anonymisation of personal data should be decided on a

¹²⁷ See D.5.1 Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – v1, March 2022

¹²⁸ See D2.2 Data Management Plan -v1,

¹²⁹ EDPB, 21 April 2020, Guidelines 04/2020 on the use of location data and contact tracing tools in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak on 15 December 2020.

¹³⁰ Recital 26 GDPR

case-by-case basis. The EDPB identifies two main families of anonymization techniques, randomization and generalization of data and warns that both techniques “have gaps, even if each of them may be appropriate, depending on the circumstances and the context.”¹³¹ When choosing to apply a given technique, three key anonymization risks must be considered:

1. Individualization, which is the ability to isolate some or all of the records identifying an individual from the data set;
2. Correlation, which consists of the ability to link together, at least, two records relating to the same data subject or to a group of data subjects (either in the same database or in two different databases);
3. Inference, which is the possibility of inferring, with a high degree of probability, the value of an attribute from the values of a set of other attributes ¹³².

A successful anonymization process that meets the three aforementioned criteria would resist identification attempts using the means most likely to be reasonably implemented by the data controller or third parties. Where one of the criteria is not fulfilled, a thorough assessment of the identified risks should be carried out and, where appropriate, a combination of techniques should be used to enhance the reliability of the result.¹³³ The anonymization of data can take place in several steps depending on the case, what matters is the ultimate result. Whenever anonymisation is not possible, proper pseudonymisation should be the number one safety measure to implement.

The DMP in its section 2.5.2 has per objective: identify the de-personalisation techniques to be used on each of the different RWD datasets. At the time of writing there is no further information about which technique will be used in each case.

4.3.3 WHAT DOES PSEUDONYMISATION MEAN?

<p>Pseudonymization Article 4(5) of the GDPR ¹³⁴</p>	<p><i>the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person;</i></p>
---	---

Pseudonymisation is a processing activity aimed at mitigating the risks towards the data subject by making its identification impossible without the use of additional information. Differently from anonymization, it does not aim to prevent a data subject from being identifiable. In that sense, it is regarded as an appropriate technical measure for enhancing data protection and is mentioned explicitly for the design and security of its data processing.

As a safeguard and a security measure for controllers and processors, pseudonymisation represents a practical implementation of some main data protection principles, particularly, purpose limitation, data minimisation and data protection by default and by design.¹³⁵ Due to its value towards reducing risks for

¹³¹ See EDPB former Article 29 Working Party Opinion on Anonymisation Techniques, April 2014. 0829/14/EN WP216, p.11.

¹³² Ibid., p. 13.

¹³³ Ibid. pp. 26-27.

¹³⁴Pseudonymization is not explicitly mentioned in the legal definition of the CoE Modernized Convention 108. However, the Explanatory Report of Modernized Convention 108 clearly states that “the use of a pseudonym or of any digital identifier/ digital identity does not lead to anonymization of the data as the data subject can still be identifiable or individualized”. Therefore, “[p]seudonymous data is [...] to be considered a personal data [...]” covered by Modernized Convention 108.

¹³⁵ Article 6(4) of the GDPR

data subjects, it should also be considered decisive with regard to access management policies.”¹³⁶

In practice pseudonymisation may involve removing unique identifiers such as names, social security numbers, and dates of birth.¹³⁷

4.3.4 PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT ON THE MES-COBRA D “DE PERSONALISATION” MODULE

Despite not being yet operational, at the time of writing, the de-personalisation module¹³⁸ in MES-CoBraD is foreseen to operate on five steps, combining both automatic and manual processes (S).¹³⁹ Whether the module will render the personal data anonymous or pseudonymous cannot be concluded beforehand, and it will depend on the adequate execution of each of the five de-personalisation steps:

S1- Patient’s data collection and preparation: Scientists and Clinicians preliminarily prepare patients’ data to be submitted to the de-personalisation module. In MES-CoBraD, this will be done by the medical partners at their premises.

S2- De-personalisation module configuration: Scientists and clinicians configure the module. In MES-CoBraD the de-personalisation module will contemplate different protocols for each type of RWD.

S3- Data de-personalisation through the module: Having selected the different method of de-personalisation (i.e. anonymisation or pseudonymisation), the de-personalisation module will suggest, through forms, a list of pre-selected fields of identifiers that need to be removed.

S4- Manual verification of the de-personalised module: once an output is obtained, a notification alert will be displayed to the user requesting confirmation on whether the data identifiers have been effectively removed. For the purposes of MES-CoBraD, only the medical partners will be in charge of verifying that the data has been successfully de-personalised as intended. If the de-personalisation has not been completely successful, the clinician or scientist will be able to remove them manually.

S5- Verified data submission: after revision and confirmation, the user will upload the data into the platform, making them available to other components and users.

As expressed above, if the de-personalisation module has successfully anonymised the dataset, the data uploaded is no longer personal data, and therefore no processing of personal data will take place at the MES-CoBraD platform.¹⁴⁰ Alternatively, if the data remains personal data, the GDPR will continue to apply to the dataset once at the platform. In that respect and irrespective of where the information enabling the identification of a data subject is stored, if an individual can potentially be identified, it will still be considered personal data.¹⁴¹ The risk of re-identification of the data must be assessed by means of “test

¹³⁶ G. Verhenneman et al., ‘How GDPR Enhances Transparency and Fosters Pseudonymisation in Academic Medical Research’, *European Journal of Health Law* 27, no. 1 (4 March 2020): 35–57, <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12251009>.

¹³⁷ S. Lusignan, ‘Effective pseudonymisation and explicit statements of public interest to ensure the benefits of sharing health data for research, quality improvement and health service management outweigh the risks,’ *Informatics in Primary Care* 21(2) (2014) 61-63.

¹³⁸ VUB suggested changing the name from anonymisation module to “de-personalisation module.” Anonymised or pseudonymised data is an outcome of the process, if it ends up being one or the other will depend on how it was carried.

¹³⁹ D.5.1. Data integration, harmonisation, sharing and security – v1, March 2022

¹⁴⁰ See AEPD-EDPS joint paper on 10 misunderstandings related to anonymization, April 2021, p. 5, available at https://edps.europa.eu/system/files/2021-04/21-04-27_aepd-edps_anonymisation_en_5.pdf, (last accessed 13 February 2022).

¹⁴¹ In *Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland*, the CJEU considered that it was not required that all information enabling the identification of the data subject must be held in the hands of “one person” for that information to constitute personal data.

of reasonable likelihood of identification.¹⁴²

When performing the test, the controller must take into account “the time, effort or resource needed in light of the nature of the data, the context of their use, the available re-identification technologies and related costs”.¹⁴³

Generally speaking, and regardless of the individual assessment required for each type of RWD and its applicable de-personalisation technique, if the responsible medical partners keep information enabling the re-identification of the data subject, then the data uploaded into the platform should be considered personal data to the effects of the GDPR.

It is recommended that the de-personalisation taking place at MES-CoBraD is considered a safeguard or safety measure rather than a derogatory tool of data protection obligations.

It is also recommended that for the whole duration of the project, pseudonymisation is adopted by default to the data uploaded in the platform and, furthermore, that medical partners commit not to allow the re-identification of data subjects the data refers to.

4.4 CONTROLLERSHIP: ROLE AND OBLIGATIONS IN MES-COBRA D

Under data protection law, those entities involved in processing might be controllers, processors, and/or recipients. Fundamentally, the qualification as one or the other depends on the role a party has in determining the purposes and means of a specific data processing activity. Each category has different legal obligations and duties attached. This said, it should be borne in mind that when assessing controllership, a mere theoretical approach is insufficient.

This section sets the core elements to perform a factual assessment of the circumstances of each activity carried by the entities involved in the project. Based on the guidelines of the EDPB, the concepts of controller, processors, and joint controllership are introduced and discussed in the particular case of the MES-CoBraD research activities. In addition, the analysis also offers a preliminary guide to the controllership structure of the MES-CoBraD platform.

4.4.1 WHO IS A CONTROLLER?

<p>Controller</p> <p>Article 4 (7) of the GDPR</p>	<p>controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law</p>
--	--

The definitory aspect of controllership is the capacity to determine or influence the purposes and means of the processing. Whether this power derives from a legal designation or factual circumstances must be decided on a case-by-case basis.

A controller can be linked either to a single activity within the processing lifecycle of a dataset or to several sets of operations. In practice, this means that the control exercised by a particular entity may extend to the entirety of processing at issue but may also be limited to a particular stage in the processing.¹⁴⁴

¹⁴² EDPB, 21 April 2020, Guidelines 04/2020 on the use of location data and contact tracing tools in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak; See also EDPB, 15 December 2020

¹⁴³ Council of Europe, Committee of Convention 108 (2017), Guidelines on the Protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, 23 January 2017, para 6.2 .

¹⁴⁴ EDPB, 7 July, 2020 Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR v2.0, p 40; See also Explanatory Report of Modernised Convention 108, para. 22.

Jurisdictionally, the representative of the controller must be established “in one of the Member States where the data subjects, whose personal data are processed in relation to the offering of goods and services to them, or whose behaviour is monitored” (Article 27 of the GDPR) ¹⁴⁵. If no representative is designated, legal action can still be initiated against the controller or the processor themselves.¹⁴⁶

4.4.2 WHAT IS A PROCESSOR ?

Processor Article 4 (8) of the GDPR ¹⁴⁷	'processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller;
--	---

The processor is a separate entity of the controller who is entrusted with the execution of certain tasks for the benefit of the controller. The commands might be general or specific, what truly defines the role of the processor is its influence on the decision-making process. Accordingly, the processor cannot process data without the permission of the controller and its instructions. A processor would infringe the GDPR if ignores or exceeds the controller’s instructions. In the event of surpassing its mandate, the processor would be considered a controller for that processing. Furthermore, ignoring the controller’s instructions may lead to sanctions for infringing the GDPR.¹⁴⁸

The qualification of processor and controller is always restricted to specific processing activities. This means that processors and controllers can hold distinct roles with regard to different personal data sets and their respective processing lifecycles.

4.4.3 WHAT IS A JOINT CONTROLLERSHIP?

Joint controller Article 26 of the GDPR ¹⁴⁹	Where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing, they shall be joint controllers. They shall in a transparent manner determine their respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under this Regulation, in particular as regards the exercising of the rights of the data subject and their respective duties to provide the information referred to in Articles 13 and 14, by means of an arrangement between them unless, and in so far as, the respective responsibilities of the controllers are determined by Union or Member State law to which the controllers are subject. The arrangement may designate a contact point for data subjects.
	2. The arrangement referred to in paragraph 1 shall duly reflect the respective roles and relationships of the joint controllers vis-à-vis the data subjects. The essence of the arrangement shall be made available to the data subject.
	3. Irrespective of the terms of the arrangement referred to in paragraph 1, the data subject may exercise his or her rights under this Regulation in respect of and against each of the controllers.

In the event there are two or more actors jointly determining the purpose and means of a processing activity, they are to be considered joint controllers.¹⁵⁰ In practice, “jointly” must be interpreted as meaning “together with” or “not alone.” As in the case of controllers and processors, joint controllership must be

¹⁴⁵ General Data Protection Regulation, Art. 27 (1).

¹⁴⁶ Ibid EDPB Guidelines 07/2020

¹⁴⁷ A definition that is also shared by the Modernised Convention 108 (Article 2 (f)).

¹⁴⁸ Article 28(10) of the GDPR.

¹⁴⁹ A definition shared in the modernised convention 108 (Article 2 (f) of the Modernised Convention 108

¹⁵⁰ Similarly, the Explanatory Report of Modernised Convention 108 states that multiple controllers or co-controllership is also possible within the CoE framework.

assessed on a factual and not theoretical basis. The criteria for joint controllership and the extent to which two or more actors jointly exercise control over a data processing activity may take different forms and they do not necessarily need to carry equal responsibilities. In this respect, the EDPB distinguishes between two types of joint participation by two or more entities:¹⁵¹

- › Common decisions: when the decision the process is taken jointly “with the more common understanding of the term jointly.”
- › Converging decisions: when decisions over the purpose and means of the processing complement each other and are necessary for the processing to take place in such manner that they have a tangible impact on the determination of the purposes and means of processing. Convergence is found in those cases where the “processing would not be possible without both parties’ participation in the purposes and means in the sense that the processing by each party is inextricably linked.

The joint controller’s regime on the basis of converging decisions differs from a controller-processor relationship insofar the processor does not process the data for its own purposes but conducts the processing on behalf of the controller.

4.4.4 DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN CONTROLLERS-JOINT CONTROLLERS AND PROCESSORS.

Controllership is based on identifying who determines the "purpose" and the "means" of a processing activity. The question is where to draw the line between decisions that are reserved to the controller and decisions that can be left to the discretion of the processor. While in some occasions, both means and purposes of a processing activity are clearly decided by one entity, there are other cases where multiple actors decide on different levels. As a result, processing activities might end up being divided into smaller processing operations the controllership each of which needs to be assessed individually.

In order to clarify the roles within a processing activity, three considerations must be raised with regards to: i. the access to personal data being processed; ii. The stages of the processing lifecycle and iii) the level of responsibility between partners.

a. Access to personal data

When defining controllership, the access to the personal data is not always conclusive. The fact that one of the parties does not have access to personal data processed is not sufficient to exclude joint controllership. What matters is the influence of the different entities on the determination of the purposes and means of a processing activity.

This has been sustained by the CJEU in the *Wirtschaftsakademie* case¹⁵². In that case Facebook and a German school administering a fan site within the social network were regarded as joint controllers of the personal data resulting from it.

Having been sanctioned by the German DPA, the German school brought a complaint against the decision, arguing that “it was not responsible under data protection law for the processing of the data by Facebook or the cookies which Facebook installed” on the basis of lack access to the data.

The CJEU concluded that both Facebook and the owner of the fan site had to be considered as joint controllers regardless of who had actual access to personal data.¹⁵³

¹⁵¹ Ibid EDPB Guidelines 07/2020

¹⁵² Judgment in *Wirtschaftsakademie*, C-210/16, ECLI:EU:C:2018:388, paragraph 38.

¹⁵³ The decision recalled the arguments previously raised in the *Jehovah’s witnesses’* case by the same Court. There the CJEU

b. The stages of the processing lifecycle

By reference to the decision of the CJEU in the *Fashion ID* case¹⁵⁴, the EDPB holds that “an entity will be considered as joint controller with the other(s) only in respect to those operations for which it determines, jointly with others, the means, and the purposes of the data processing”.¹⁵⁵ As a result, the joint controllership regime is factually determined with regards to the processing lifecycle and all its different processing activities.

Whenever one entity decides alone the purposes and means of the processing preceding or subsequent to those that are decided jointly that entity will have to be considered as the sole controller of this preceding or subsequent operation.

Whether a specific processing activity that is (apparently) isolated belongs to a set “set of operations” must be checked by examining the subjacent purpose motivating it.¹⁵⁶ Thus, a sequence or set of processing operations involving several actors may also take place for the same purpose(s), in which case it is possible that the processing involves one or more joint controllers.

c. Level of responsibility

The identification of controllers, processors, and joint controllerships is important to clarify the allocation of obligations towards compliance with data protection rules. When it comes to discuss responsibility of joint controllers, it must be noted that it does not necessarily imply equal responsibility for the various operators involved in the processing of personal data. On the contrary, the level of responsibility of the different entities within a joint controllership will depend on how they are involved at different processing stages, and to which degree.

4.4.5 DATA PROCESSING RESPONSIBILITY

The following sections assess the different elements forming the concept of the controller, following the EDPB’s deconstruction on the concept and applying to the particular case of MES-CoBraD : 1) “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body” 2) “who determines” 3) “alone or jointly with others” 4) the “purposes and means” of the processing of personal data.

4.4.5.1 Processing entities in MES-CoBraD

There are three separate groups of entities participating in the MES-CoBraD joint research project. According to their role, they can be separated in 1. Medical Partners; 2. Technical Partners; and 3. Supporting Partners.

The Medical partners lead the collection and exploitation of RWD, and, jointly with technical partners, decide on the components and functioning of the MES-CoBraD-platform. Additionally, the consortium is completed by the third category of entities leading legal, dissemination and administrative activities.

While all partners decide jointly to undertake and participate in the scientific research, not all partners

observed the existence of a joint controllership between the religious community and the members engaging with the door to door preaching and responsible for collecting the personal data. The court argued that both actors were to considered joint controllers, irrespective of the fact that the religious community did not have access to the data obtained by the preachers. Furthermore the decision also concluded that it was not necessary to establish that the community had given its members written guidelines or instructions in relation to the data processing.

¹⁵⁴ Judgment in *Fashion ID*, C-40/17, ECLI:EU:2018:1039, paragraph 74

¹⁵⁵ Ibid EDPB Guidelines 07/2020

¹⁵⁶ Ibid. The EDPB states that “it is possible that at “micro-level” the different processing operations of the chain appear as disconnected, as each of them may have a different purpose. However, it is necessary to double-check whether at “macro-level” these processing operations should not be considered as a “set of operations” pursuing a joint purpose using jointly defined means.”

are equally responsible for all data processing activities taking place during the project.

4.4.5.2 What does “determining” mean?

The influence of an actor over a data processing activity is defined by the exercise of decision-making power in its means and purposes. In that way, the controller appears as the entity deciding certain key elements about the processing. When defining the controllership of certain processing, it is necessary to look at the specific processing operations in question and understand who participates in their definition and execution.

The concept of controller is “functional” and based on a factual assessment of the processing activities. In practice, this means that what determines the controllership is not the type of entity but its influence over the activities in the data processing lifecycle.¹⁵⁷ The entity(ies) exerting a decision-making power over the purposes and means of the processing will be considered controller(s). This does not mean that the processor only acts on command, in certain occasions, it will also be able to make some decisions in relation to the processing.¹⁵⁸

4.4.5.3 What does “purpose and means” mean ?

The principle of purpose limitation, states that “data must be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes”¹⁵⁹. The concepts of purpose and means appear to address such key aspects:

The purpose anticipates an intended outcome for which data processing operations occurs. In other words, the purpose of processing answers “why” the processing takes place. In Mes-CoBraD, the purpose is determined by the consortium compromise to collaborate in scientific research in order to develop the MES-CoBraD platform.

The means determine the methods how a result is obtained, or an end is achieved. Considering the flexibility recognised by the EDPB, what must be clarified is which decisions on the means should lead controllership and which ones can be left at the discretion of the processor.¹⁶⁰ From this a distinction is drawn between essential and non-essential means.

On the one hand, “essential means” are considered traditionally and inherently reserved to the controller. Together with the purpose of processing, the essential means are also intricately linked to the question of whether the processing is lawful, necessary, and proportionate¹⁶¹:

- › Which data shall be processed?
- › Whose personal data are being processed?
- › For how long they shall be processed?
- › Who shall have access to them?

On the other hand, the processor can also determine “non-essential means.” Non-essential means concern more practical aspects of implementation, such as the choice for a particular type of hardware

¹⁵⁷ Ibid EDPB Guidelines 07/2020. pp 11, and 13

¹⁵⁸ The EDPB has recognised the need for further guidance when it comes to borderline cases between controllers and processors. In those cases, answering the “why” and the “how”, should entail the qualification of an entity as a controller and to what extent a processor may make decisions of its own.

¹⁵⁹ Article 5 (b) of the GDPR

¹⁶⁰ Ibid EDPB Guidelines 07/2020, pp. 15.

¹⁶¹ These aspects are defined in the D3.2 Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation – v2. Information concerning the storage rules of the data processed in the MES-CoBraD platform and the access to the same is also provided in D2.2 Data Management Plan -v1 project.

or software, the detailed security measures which may be left to the processor to decide on.

4.4.6 THE PROCESSING ARRANGEMENT FOR THE SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH PERFORMED AT MES-COBRA D.

In MES-CoBraD, there is a joint agreement to process data in order to carry out scientific research and ultimately develop a platform. Nevertheless, there are also several sub-processing activities for which the influence in the decision-making process is not equally shared among partners. As a result, the responsibility between partners cannot be the same.

Due to the special sensitivity of the personal data involved, and in line with the principle of transparency and accountability, it is recommended that the consortium enters into a data processing arrangement to identify and allocate the relevant responsibilities of each partner.

4.5 DATA PROTECTION PRINCIPLES IN MES-COBRA D

The main effect of data protection frameworks is the obligation for controllers and processors to observe and comply with its principles. The following lines examine the data protection principles in MES-CoBraD from a twofold perspective. First, focusing on the obligations and the special regime granted to scientific research activities involving human participants.¹⁶² Second, based the principles of data protection, by design and by default, an operational list of key recommendations will be provided to technical partners to embed the principles into the platform design.¹⁶³

It must be noted that at the time of writing, the functioning of the platform's component has not yet been completely defined (i.e. the user interface).¹⁶⁴ Nevertheless, MES-CoBraD should aim from the early stage of its "architectural building", to be designed taking into account the observance of data protection principles and respect data subjects' rights and freedoms.

4.5.1 DEROGATIONS UNDER THE SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH REGIME

The GDPR understands that the processing of personal data, including special categories of data, for the purpose of scientific research is a desirable and a priori compatible with its provisions. To that end it grants a special regime with derogations from data protection principles. This regime is conditioned by the controller's adoption of adequate technical and organisational safeguards ensuring data minimisation as well as other principles.¹⁶⁵

The GDPR's defines scientific research in its article 89, clarifying its scope in its recital 159 as follow: "the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes should be interpreted in a broad manner including, for example, technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research".¹⁶⁶

¹⁶² Article 89 of the GDPR

¹⁶³ The list of recommendations is based on the EDPB guidelines on EDPB, 13 November 2019, Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.

¹⁶⁴ See MES-CoBraD, D.6.1 MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Prototype, March 2022.

¹⁶⁵ The EDPS has recognised the value of coupling information from registries in medical research and social sciences. However it alerts on the risks of understanding this regime in a way that " the essence of the right to data protection is emptied out, and this includes data subject rights, appropriate organisational and technical measures against accidental or unlawful destruction, loss or alteration, and the supervision of an independent authority". EDPS, Assessing the necessity of measures that limit the fundamental right to the protection of personal data: A Toolkit, 11 April 2017, and discussion (footnote 8) of CJEU judgments in Schrems, CJEU Joined Cases C-293/12 and C-594/12 Digital Rights Ireland 8 April 2014 and Tele2 Sverige AB

¹⁶⁶The EDPB in its endorsed opinion on consent 17/EN WP259 , has narrowed it down arguing that its scope should not be stretched beyond its common meaning and interpreted as a research project set up in accordance with relevant sector-related methodological and ethical standards, in conformity with good practice.

<p>Safeguards and derogations relating to processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes</p> <p>Article 89 GDPR</p> <p>See also Relevant recitals 156, 157, 158, and 159</p>	<p>1. Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes, or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing, which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.</p>
	<p>2. Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.</p>
	<p>3. Where personal data are processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, Union or Member State law may provide for derogations from the rights referred to in Articles 15, 16, 18, 19, 20 and 21 subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article in so far as such rights are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes, and such derogations are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes.</p>
	<p>4. Where processing referred to in paragraphs 2 and 3 serves at the same time another purpose, the derogations shall apply only to processing for the purposes referred to in those paragraphs.</p>

4.5.2 LAWFULNESS OF PROCESSING

<p>Lawfulness, fairness, and transparency</p> <p>(Art. 5(1) (a) of the GDPR)</p>	<p>Personal data shall be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject</p>
--	--

The definition of lawfulness in the context of a data processing activity includes three elements, the legal basis, fairness, and its transparency. During the project, these aspects must be assessed at two levels: i) at the clinical site level and ii) at a platform level: where the data is stored after being de-personalised and uploaded.

4.5.2.1 Legal basis to process MES CoBraD RWD: consent, public interest, or legitimate interest

Pursuant to the principle of lawfulness, all processing of personal data shall be based on one, or multiple grounds set out in Article 6(1) of the GDPR:

- (a) the data subject has given free, voluntary, and specific consent;
- (b) performance of a contract to which data subject is a party;
- (c) compliance with a legal obligation of the controller;
- (d) protection the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;
- (e) the activity carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority;
- (f) legitimate interests pursued by the controller or third party, as long as it is not overridden by fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject.

Among these, explicit consent, public interest, and legitimate interest are the three preferred options for

the EDPB.¹⁶⁷ The decision to rely on one or the other will need to consider several aspects of the RWD, including its type, level of sensitiveness and the adequacy towards purpose compatibility.

Explicit consent: (Article 6(1)(a) + Article 9(2)(a)), + Article 89 (1)

Consent to participate in research activity (i.e. clinical trial or test) must be distinguished from the consent as a legal basis for the processing of personal data. Under the GDPR, a valid consent must be freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous, and explicit. In the event the controller wishes to rely on consent for the processing of sensitive data in the course of a research activity, the data controllers should duly consider the WP29 Guidelines on consent, and check if all the conditions are met.¹⁶⁸

Due to the complexities in reaching and maintaining all the requirements of explicit consent through the various stages of a research project, the EDPB has warned data controllers about the risks of relying exclusively on individuals' consent as a legal basis. Alternatively, to consent the EDPB suggests the lawful grounds of processing provided under public interest or legitimate interest are more appropriate.¹⁶⁹

Public interest: (Article 6(1)(e) + Article 9(2)(i)), + Article 89 (1)

The processing of personal data by data controllers could be considered "necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest" pursuant to Article 6(1)(e) GDPR. Article 6(3) GDPR further provides that this basis shall be laid down by Union or Member State law and that the purpose of the processing shall be laid down in that legal basis.¹⁷⁰

The processing of personal data could be considered as necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest when the conduct of clinical trials or tests directly falls within the mandate, missions, and tasks vested in a public or private body by national law. If applicable, the relevant medical partner will need to assess this considering its own national legislation.

Legitimate interests of the controller: (Article 6(1)(f) + Article 9(2)(i) or (j) + Article 89 (1)

The legitimate interests for the processing of special categories of data will apply only when Article 9 GDPR provides for a specific derogation from the general prohibition to process special categories of data. In the case of MES-CoBraD for "scientific purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law" (Article 9(2)(j)).¹⁷¹ The GDPR allows for the processing of sensitive data for medical research if it is authorised by law, it adheres to the principle of proportionality, respects the essence of the right to protection of personal data, and provides specific safeguards for the protection of individuals' fundamental rights and interests (Article 9(1)(j) of GDPR). As recognised by the EDPB, reliance on legitimate interest as the legal ground, is considered advisable for the processing of sensitive data when conducting general medical research.¹⁷²

The national laws regulating the derogations concerning the processing of personal data concerning health for the purposes of scientific research have not been fully unified within the EU.

¹⁶⁷ EDPB, 21 April 2020, Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak.

¹⁶⁸ WP29, 10 April 2018, Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679 of the former Article 29 Working-Party, WP259 rev.01, 17EN, page 27 (endorsed by the EDPB). Available at https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/item-detail.cfm?item_id=623051 (Last accessed 20 February 2022).

¹⁶⁹ *ibid*

¹⁷⁰ Recital (54) of the GDPR states that "the processing of special categories of personal data may be necessary for reasons of public interest in the areas of public health without consent of the data subject. Such processing should be subject to suitable and specific measures so as to protect the rights and freedoms of natural persons."

¹⁷¹ As indicated by the EDPB, the processing operations purely related to research activities cannot be derived from a legal obligation, namely a contract.

¹⁷² EDPB, 21 April, 2020, Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak.

Legal basis at MES-CoBraD

At the time of collection, the relevant medical partner will need to identify an adequate legal basis pursuant to EU and its national law. It will need to ensure that they have a legal basis for the processing RWD, and that its further processing during MES-CoBraD is not incompatible with its original purpose.¹⁷³ In light of the principle of purpose limitation, further processing and purpose compatibility will need to be evaluated taking into account the technical and organisational measures adopted by the controller.¹⁷⁴

4.5.2.1.1 Lawfulness by design and by default

Lawfulness-Key design and default elements		
1.	Relevance	The controller of the dataset should be responsible for applying the correct legal basis to the processing, prior to the upload into the platform.
2.	Differentiation	There is a need to differentiate between the legal basis used for processing activities for medical or healthcare purposes and those aimed at scientific research.
3.	Specified purpose	The appropriate legal basis must be clearly connected to the specific purpose of processing.
4.	Necessary	Processing must be necessary for the purpose to be lawful. It is an objective test that involves an accurate assessment of realistic alternatives for achieving the purpose.
5.	Autonomy	The data subject should be granted the highest degree of autonomy as possible with respect to control over personal data.
6.	Consent Withdrawal	In the event consent is the chosen legal basis, the processing shall facilitate withdrawal of consent. Withdrawal shall be as easy as giving consent. If not, any given consent is not valid.
7.	Balancing of interests	Where legitimate interests are the legal basis, the controller must carry out an objectively weighted balancing of interests. There shall be measures and safeguards to mitigate the negative impact on the data subjects, and the controller should disclose their assessment of the balancing of interests.
8.	Predetermination	The legal basis shall be established before the processing takes place.
9.	Cessation	If the legal basis ceases to apply, the processing shall cease accordingly. Only the medical partner as controller of the data can adequately comply with this responsibility.
10.	Adjust	If there is a valid change of legal basis for the processing, the actual processing must be adjusted in accordance with the new legal basis.
11.	Default configurations	Processing must be limited to what the legal basis strictly gives grounds for.
12.	Allocation of responsibility	Whenever joint controllership is envisaged, the parties must apportion in a clear and transparent way their respective responsibilities vis-à-vis the data subject.

¹⁷³ In the case of existing or retrospective data, the purpose and the legal basis that enabled its storage and subsequent processing based on its national legislation will need to be identified. For new or prospective data, the purpose and the legal basis will have to be chosen at the time of collection based on the relevant national law. See MES-CoBraD D2.2 Data Management Plan-v1; see also upcoming iterations of the present deliverable.

¹⁷⁴ Article 89 of the GDPR

4.5.2.2 Fairness

Fair processing governs primarily the relationship between the controller and the data subject.¹⁷⁵ Controllers should notify data subjects and the general public that they will process data in a lawful and transparent manner and must be able to proactively demonstrate the compliance of processing operations with the GDPR. When required, data subjects should be aware of potential risks.¹⁷⁶

4.5.2.2.1 Fairness by design and by default

Fairness-Key design and default elements		
13.	Autonomy	Data subjects shall be granted the highest degree of autonomy possible with respect to control over their personal data. With regards to the data processing at MES-CoBraD platform, the derogations in the special regime of article 89 will be considered.
14.	Interaction	Data subjects must be able to communicate and exercise their rights with the controller. Regarding the data processing at MES-CoBraD platform, the derogations in the special regime of article 89 will need to be considered.
15.	Expectation	Processing should correspond with data subjects' expectations.
16.	Non-discrimination	Controllers must not discriminate against data subjects. At a development level, this should be considered when defining the exploitation capabilities of the MES-CoBraD platform.
17.	Non-exploitation	The controller shall not exploit the needs or vulnerabilities of data subjects. At a development level, this should be considered when defining the exploitation capabilities of the MES-CoBraD platform.
18.	Consumer choice	The controller should not "lock in" their users. Whenever a service or a good is personalized or proprietary, it may create a lock-in to the service or good. If it is difficult for the data subject to change controllers due to this, which may not be fair.
19.	Power balance	Asymmetric power balances shall be avoided or mitigated when possible. Controllers should not transfer the risks of the enterprise to the data subjects.
20.	Respect to the rights and freedoms	The controller must respect the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects and implement appropriate measures and safeguards to not violate these rights and freedoms.

4.5.2.3 Transparency

The requirement of transparency establishes an obligation for the controller to adopt appropriate measures for keeping the data subjects informed, in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, about how their data are being used¹⁷⁷.

The principle of transparency requires that any information and communication relating to the processing of those personal data be easily accessible and easy to understand, and that clear and plain language be used. Those principal concerns, in particular, information to the data subjects on the identity of the controller and the purposes of the processing and further information to ensure fair and transparent

¹⁷⁵ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law, p. 118

¹⁷⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷⁷ Article 12(1), GDPR. Also see European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018, Handbook on Data European Protection Law, p. 120.

processing in respect of the natural persons concerns and their right to obtain confirmation and communication of personal data concerning them which are being processed.

Natural persons should be made aware of risks, rules, safeguards, and rights in relation to the processing of personal data and how to exercise their rights in relation to such processing. In particular, the specific purposes for which personal data are processed should be explicit and legitimate and determined at the time of the collection of the personal data.¹⁷⁸

The principle of transparency is closely related with the right to information observed in article 13 and 14 of the GDPR. In the context of the project, activities the derogations foreseen in the special regime must be contemplated.

4.5.2.3.1 Transparency by design and by default

Transparency-Key design and default elements		
21.	Clarity	Information shall be in clear and plain language, concise and intelligible.
22.	Semantics	Communication shall have a clear meaning to the audience in question.
23.	Accessibility	Information shall be easily accessible for the data subject.
24.	Contextual	Information shall be provided at the relevant time and in the appropriate form.
25.	Relevance	Information shall be relevant and applicable to the specific data subject.
26.	Universal design	Information shall be accessible to all, this includes use of machine readable languages to facilitate and automate readability and clarity.
27.	Comprehensible	Data subjects shall have a fair understanding of what they can expect with regards to the processing of their personal data, particularly when the data subjects are children or other vulnerable groups.
28.	Multi Chanel	Information should be provided in different channels and media, beyond the textual, to increase the probability for the information to effectively reach the data subject

4.5.3 PURPOSE LIMITATION: FURTHER PROCESSING AND THE PRESUMPTION OF COMPATIBILITY

Purpose limitation Article 5(1) (b) of the GDPR	Personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation');
---	---

The principle of purpose limitation requires the identification of a specified explicit and legitimate purpose prior a processing begins¹⁷⁹. With regards to retrospective data as well as for prospective data collected for a purpose different from scientific research, the processing in MES-CoBraD of data will need to satisfy the requirement of purpose compatibility. This might present problems in those cases where the controller relies on consent as a legal basis for processing data.¹⁸⁰

Further processing is allowed when it is done for archiving, public interest, scientific, historical, statistical

¹⁷⁸ Recital 39 of the GDPR.

¹⁷⁹ Article 5.1(b) of the GDPR

¹⁸⁰ For more on consent and issues associated with the secondary use of data see: P. Boddington, L. Curren, J. Kaye, N. Kanellopoulou, K. Melham, H. Gowansa and N. Hawkinsa, 'Consent Forms in Genomics: The Difference between Law and Practice,' *The European Journal of Health Law* 18 (2011) 491-519.; See also Kosta, E. (2013). *Consent in European data protection law.* (Nijhoff Studies in European Union Law; No. 3). Martinus Nijhoff.

or research purposes, as soon as technical and organisational measures are adopted.¹⁸¹ In that sense, under the special regime, the controller is able to further process the data without the need for a new legal basis.

This said, it should be noted that, even when the presumption of compatibility applies, the scientific research making use of “re-purposed data,” will need to be conducted in compliance with all other relevant applicable provisions of data protection.

4.5.3.1 Purpose limitation by design and by default

Purpose Limitation- Key design and default elements		
29.	Predetermination	The legitimate purposes must be determined before the design of the processing.
30.	Specificity	The purposes must be specific to the processing and make it explicitly clear why personal data is being processed.
31.	Purpose orientation	The purpose of processing should guide the design of the processing and set processing boundaries.
32.	Necessity	The purpose determines what personal data is necessary for the processing.
33.	Compatibility	Any new purpose must be compatible with the original purpose for which the data was collected and guide relevant changes in design.
34.	Limit further processing	The controller should not connect datasets or perform any further processing for new incompatible purposes.
35.	Review	The controller must regularly review whether the processing is necessary for the purposes for which the data was collected and evaluate the design against purpose limitation.
36.	Technical limitations of reuse	The controller should use technical measures, including hashing and cryptography, to limit the possibility of repurposing personal data.

4.5.4 DATA MINIMISATION

Data minimisation Article 5 (1) (c) of the GDPR	Personal data shall be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
--	---

The principle of data minimisation aims to “minimise” the data processed in a way that only the data that is adequate, relevant, and strictly necessary for the purpose is processed. As such, it represents a practical implementation of the principle of necessity.

The minimisation of data can also refer to the degree of identification of a data subject¹⁸². It follows that whenever it is not necessary to identify, the data should be de-personalised as much as possible. Anonymisation fulfils, to best extent possible, the principle of data minimisation. Alternatively, and while it does not render the data anonymous, pseudonymisation is considered an appropriate technical

¹⁸¹ Article 89(1) of the GDPR

¹⁸²EDPB, 13 November 2019, Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.pp.19

measure for enhancing data protection pursuant to the data minimisation principle.

The de-personalisation module at the MES-CoBraD platform aims to, at least, pseudonymise the personal data uploaded in it.

4.5.4.1 Data minimisation by design and by default

Data minimisation-Key design and default elements		
37.	Data avoidance	Avoid processing personal data altogether when this is possible for the relevant purpose.
38.	Relevance	Personal data shall be relevant to the processing in question, and the controller shall be able to demonstrate this relevance
39.	Necessity	Each personal data element shall be necessary for the specified purposes and should only be processed if it is not possible to fulfil the purpose by other means.
40.	Limitation	Limit the amount of personal data collected to what is necessary for the purpose
41.	Aggregation	Use aggregated data when possible
42.	Pseudonymisation	Pseudonymize personal data as soon as it is no longer necessary to have directly identifiable personal data, and store identification keys separately
43.	Anonymisation and deletion	Where personal data is not, or no longer necessary for the purpose, personal data shall be anonymized or deleted
44.	Data flow	The data flow shall be made efficient enough to not create more copies, or entry points for data collection than necessary
45.	State of the art	The controller should apply available and suitable technologies for data avoidance and minimisation.

4.5.5 ACCURACY

Data accuracy Article 5 (1) (d) of the GDPR	Personal data shall be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, regarding to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased, or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
--	---

The personal data processed during MES-CoBraD project only aims at facilitating the development of the platform, no decision or diagnosis will be carried based on it that might affect a data subject. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the data stored at the platform remains relevant in order to fulfil with the project's data management obligations, for instance actin upon an eventual data subject request. Also, the principle of accuracy remains fundamental for medical partners with regards to the data stored at their premises, in order to address any potential request from data subject.

4.5.5.1 Accuracy by design and by default

Accuracy- Key design and default elements		
46.	Data Source	Data sources should be dependable in terms of data accuracy
47.	Degree of accuracy	Each personal data element shall be as accurate as necessary for the specified purposes.
48.	Measurably accurate	Reduce the number of false positives/negatives.
49.	Verification	Depending on the nature of the data, in relation to how often it may change, the controller should verify the correctness of personal data with the data subject before and at various stages of the processing.
50.	Erasure/rectification	The controller must erase or rectify inaccurate data without delay.
51.	Accumulated errors	Controllers must mitigate the effect of an accumulated error in the processing chain.
52.	Access	Data subjects should be given an overview and easy access to personal data in order to control accuracy and rectify as needed.
53.	Continued accuracy	Personal data should be accurate at all stages of the processing, tests of accuracy should be conducted at critical steps
54.	Up to date	Personal data shall be updated if necessary for the purpose.
55.	Data design	Use of technological and organisational design features to decrease inaccuracy, e.g. drop down lists with limited values, internal policies, and legal criteria.

4.5.6 STORAGE LIMITATION

<p>Storage limitation</p> <p>Article 5 (1) (e) of the GDPR</p>	<p>Personal data shall be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1), subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject ('storage limitation');</p>
--	--

The principle of storage limitation aims to technically ensure that data is not processed longer than necessary. The measures and safeguards adopted are instrumental to the effectiveness of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects, specifically, the right to erasure, the right to object and profiling.

4.5.6.1 Storage limitation by design and by default

Storage limitation-Key design and default elements		
56.	Deletion	Avoid processing personal data altogether when this is possible for the relevant purpose.
57.	Automation	Personal data shall be relevant to the processing in question, and the controller shall be able to demonstrate this relevance

58.	Storage criteria	Each personal data element shall be necessary for the specified purposes and should only be processed if it is not possible to fulfil the purpose by other means.
59.	Enforcement of retention policies	Limit the amount of personal data collected to what is necessary for the purpose
60.	Effectiveness of anonymization/deletion	Use aggregated data when possible
61.	Disclose rationale	Pseudonymize personal data as soon as it is no longer necessary to have directly identifiable personal data, and store identification keys separately
62.	Data flow	Controllers must beware of and seek to limit “temporary” storage of personal data
63.	Backups/logs	Controllers must determine which personal data and length of storage is necessary for back-ups and logs

4.5.7 INTEGRITY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

<p>Integrity and Confidentiality Article 5 (1) (f) of the GDPR</p>	<p>Personal data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction, or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures</p>
---	--

Researchers processing personal data have the ethical and legal obligation to ensure that participant’s information is properly protected ¹⁸³. Under data protection law, the security of processing is regulated in section 2 of the GDPR, articles 32 to 34.

The principle of security embraces the security properties of Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA), aimed at reinforcing the resilience of data processing activities.

- › Confidentiality is the protection of information from unauthorized access or disclosure
- › Integrity is the protection of information from unauthorized modification.
- › Availability ensures the timely and reliable access to and use of information and systems.

The objective is twofold, from one hand prevent data breach incidents and from the other, facilitate the proper execution of data processing tasks, the observance of data protection principles and data subject rights in a seamless manner. Along with other data protection by design and by default measures, Recital 78 suggests a responsibility on the controllers to continually assess whether they are always using the appropriate means of processing and to assess whether the chosen measures actually counter the existing vulnerabilities. In that sense, the project should conduct regular reviews of the information security measures implemented to check their efficiency.

4.5.7.1 Integrity and confidentiality by design and by default

Integrity and confidentiality -Key design and default elements

¹⁸³ European Commission, Ethics and data protection 14 November 2018; accessible at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-data-protection_en.pdf

64.	Information security management system (ISMS)	Have an operative means of managing policies and procedures for information security. For some controllers, this may be possible with the help of an ISMS.
65.	Risk Analysis	Assess the risks against the security of personal data and counter identified risks
66.	Resilience	The processing should be robust enough to withstand changes, regulatory demands, incidents, and cyber attacks
67.	Access management	Only authorized personnel shall have access to the data necessary for their processing tasks
68.	Aggregation	Use aggregated data when possible
69.	Secure transfers	Transfers shall be secured against unauthorized access and changes
70.	Secure storage	Where personal data is not, or no longer necessary for the purpose, personal data shall be anonymized or deleted
71.	Backups/logs	The data flow shall be made efficient enough to not create more copies, or entry points for data collection than necessary
72.	Special protection	The controller should apply available and suitable technologies for data avoidance and minimisation.
73.	Pseudonymization	Personal data and back-ups/logs should be pseudonymized as a security measure to minimize risks of potential data breaches, for example using hashing or encryption
74.	Security incident response management	Have in place routines and procedures to detect, handle, report, and learn from data breaches
75.	Personal data breach handling	Integrate management of notification (to the supervisory authority) and information (to data subjects) obligations in the event of a data breach into security incident management procedures
76.	Maintenance and development	Regular review and test software to uncover vulnerabilities of the systems supporting the processing

4.5.8 THE PRINCIPLE OF ACCOUNTABILITY

<p>Accountability Article 5(2) of the GDPR</p>	<p>The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, paragraph 1 ('accountability').</p>
--	---

Partners participating in the MES-CoBraD research should be able to proactively demonstrate compliance with the GDPR. Regarding medical partners, they should always apply the necessary measures within their organizations in order to be able to explain, both to the individuals concerned and to any future controls by the Data Protection Authorities, that the data protection legislation has been duly observed. Indicatively, all members have an appointed DPO or given the details of a contact point for addressing legal and ethical matters. Furthermore, all partners have signed a declaration of compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation), and the national law of the country where the partner organisation

is established¹⁸⁴

The EDPB recommends the use of key performance indicators to demonstrate the effectiveness of the measures and safeguards at implementing the data protection principles.¹⁸⁵ In this respect the updated version of this deliverable (D2.9). will recall how the key elements listed above, have been implemented into the platform.

4.6 DATA PROTECTION BY DESIGN AND BY DEFAULT AT MES-COBRA D.

Data Protection by design and by default Article 25 of the GDPR See also Recital 78	1. Taking into account the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing, as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, the controller shall, both at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself, implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, which are designed to implement data-protection principles, such as data minimisation, in an effective manner and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation and protect the rights of data subjects.
	2. The controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed. That obligation applies to the amount of personal data collected, the extent of their processing, the period of their storage and their accessibility. In particular, such measures shall ensure that by default personal data are not made accessible without the individual's intervention to an indefinite number of natural persons.
	3. An approved certification mechanism pursuant to Article 42 may be used as an element to demonstrate compliance with the requirements set out in paragraphs 1 and 2 of this Article.

The principles of data protection by design and by default suppose the controller's obligation to implement data protection principles and data subject's rights as a design and as a default property of systems and services.

By definition, the principle of data protection by design must be implemented "at the time of determining the means" of a processing activity or service. It is then that controller must think and introduce the measures and safeguards to effectively implement the data protection principles.¹⁸⁶ Nevertheless, controllers must also review the effectiveness of the measures and safeguards, during the processing. The objective is to prevent risks from ever occurring prior and while the processing activity takes place.

Pursuant to article 25(1), the controller has to 1) implement appropriate technical and organisational measures and 2) integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing so that GDPR requirements and data subject rights are observed during the processing.

There is a variety of technical or organizational measures that might serve the purpose of the principles. As long as the measures are appropriate for implementing the data protection principles effectively and proportionately against potential risks. Data protection by default aims that, by default, no more than the necessary personal data for each specific purpose of the processing is processed in compliance with the law and transparently notified to the individuals concerned. In that sense the "default settings" of the platform must be designed with data protection in mind.¹⁸⁷

¹⁸⁴ MES-CoBRaD D2.2 Data Management Plan-v1

¹⁸⁵ EDPB, 13 November 2019, Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default.

¹⁸⁶ Ibid

¹⁸⁷ Ibid. The EDPS has expressed that "while it can be argued that this obligation is already implicit in the purpose limitation" and "data minimisation" principles in both the design and operation phases, the explicit rule stresses the importance of taking technical measures to meet the expectations of the individuals whose data are processed, not to have their data processed for

The key design and default features identified in section 10 will need to be mobilised and its implementation monitored during the project in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2.

4.7 SECURITY OF THE PROCESSING IN MES-COBRAD

Researchers processing personal data have the ethical and legal obligation to ensure that participant’s information is properly protected. Under GDPR data protection law, the security of processing is regulated in articles 32 to 34 of the GDPR. This section focuses on the principle of security during the MES-CoBraD research for the data stored at the platform. The technical and organizational measures implemented by the medical partners therein are beyond the scope of this section

<p>Security of processing Article 32 of the GDPR</p> <p>See also Recital 83 of the GDPR</p>	<p>1.Taking into account the state of the art, the costs of implementation and the nature, scope, context, and purposes of processing as well as the risk of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller and the processor shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, including inter alia as appropriate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the pseudonymisation and encryption of personal data; (b) the ability to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services; (c) the ability to restore the availability and access to personal data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident; (d) a process for regularly testing, assessing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures for ensuring the security of the processing.
	<p>2.In assessing the appropriate level of security account shall be taken of the risks that are presented by processing, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed.</p>
	<p>3.Adherence to an approved code of conduct as referred to in Article 40 or an approved certification mechanism as referred to in Article 42 may be used as an element by which to demonstrate compliance with the requirements set out in paragraph 1 of this Article.</p>
	<p>4.The controller and processor shall take steps to ensure that any natural person acting under the authority of the controller or the processor who has access to personal data does not process them except on instructions from the controller unless he or she is required to do so by Union or Member State law.</p>

The processing taking place at MES-CoBraD platform must comply with the obligations provided by the GDPR, including the observation of security of obligations. The fact that the platform processes special categories of personal data (health and potentially genetic data) turn the obligation to ensure security all the most important.

At the date of writing, the following tables enumerate the security measures envisaged and the relevant work package where they are being developed: ¹⁸⁸

Table 7 MES-CoBraD Technical measures

Technical measures	Description
--------------------	-------------

other purposes than what the product and service is basically and strictly meant to do, leaving by default any further use turned off, for instance through configuration settings”.

¹⁸⁸ MES-Cobrad Grant Agreement, Part B, p.16

Depersonalisation module	Adopt technical measures that prevent the re-identification of personal data. The system shall anonymise or pseudonymise (as appropriate and technically feasible) private and/or confidential data based on types of RWD.
Encryption	Encryption is a reliable way to protect sensitive data from data breaches because it protects data through its whole lifecycle. There are numerous encryption algorithms in use, including RSA, DES, AES, and many others. All data stored within the MES-CoBraD system must be encrypted where possible. This includes and temporary data stores and caches.
Secure access platform	Adopt technical and measures that prevent the access by non-authorised third parties.
Audit module	Develop a process for regular testing, assessing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of that processing. Provide support documentation and history for security and operational actions, providing proof of data origin and integrity.

Table 8 MES-CoBraD Organisational measures

Organisational measures	Description
Transparency	The Data Management plan explains how the personal data is processed during the MES-CoBraD research.
Distribution of responsibilities and Data Processing arrangement	In order to ensure a clear distribution of responsibilities in the processing of data under the MES-CoBraD project, a Data Processing Arrangement should be adopted ¹⁸⁹ .
Establish user access protocols	Adopt ensuring that access to stored personal data will be restricted to the MES-CoBraD consortium and those who need such access for processing activities.
Confidentiality and re-identification commitments	Partners in MES- CoBraD research should formally state their agreement on not pursuing the re-identification of the pseudonymised personal data stored at the platform.

4.7.1 DATA PROCESSING RISKS

European institutions, bodies and agencies have released several guides and law on the concept of risk management.¹⁹⁰ At EU level the Network Information Security Directive 2016/1148 (NIS Directive)¹⁹¹ harmonised the concept of risk in the context of the security of ICT infrastructure.

In its article 4(9) the NIS Directive defines ‘risk’ as “any reasonably identifiable circumstance or event having a potential adverse effect on the security of network and information

¹⁸⁹ The agreement should include the roles and responsibilities of the partners, the subject matter, duration, and nature of the processing, the types of personal data concerned, the categories of data subjects concerned, obligations and rights of controllers and processors

¹⁹⁰ ENISA, March 16, 2022, Risk Management Standards 2022; <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/risk-management-standards>

¹⁹¹ Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union (NIS Directive). Compared with the definitions given by ISO standards and directives the focus here is on the threat component in relation to the source of risk not to the effect. Cf. ISO/IEC 27005 DIS (2021) Clause 8,2,3.

systems”. Examples of such risks might be i) the accidental or unlawful destruction ii) loss, iii) alteration iv) unauthorised disclosure or v) the access to processed personal data. In the context of data protection, the GDPR contemplates risk management and the assessment of security measures, as being inherently connected to the risks the controllers are responsible for. They include physical, material, or non-material damages foreseen during a processing activity.¹⁹²

The MES-CoBraD consortium will need to identify those risks that could impact the personal data processed during the project. Upcoming revisions of the deliverable will recall and update the identified risks in the context of the research activities and highlight any additional technical and organisational measures necessary,

4.7.2 DATA BREACH, ASSESSMENT AND NOTIFICATION DUTY

Personal data breach Article 4(12)	Personal data breach' means a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed
---------------------------------------	---

A data breach occurs when the data subject suffers a loss of control over their personal data, a limitation of their rights, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, pecuniary loss, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, damage to reputation, and loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy. It also includes any other significant economic or social disadvantage to those individuals.¹⁹³ In its Opinion 03/2014 on breach notification¹⁹⁴ and in its Guidelines WP 250¹⁹⁵, the WP29 categorised data breaches following the CIA information security principles, as follows: ¹⁹⁶

- › Confidentiality breach: where there is an unauthorised or accidental disclosure of, or access to, personal data.
- › Integrity breach where there is an unauthorised or accidental alteration of personal data.
- › Availability breach: where there is an accidental or unauthorised loss of access to, or destruction of, personal data.

In the event of a data breach the GDPR requires the controller to:

- i. Document the breach, including the facts relating to the breach, its effects and remedial action taken.¹⁹⁷
- ii. Notify the personal data breach to the supervisory authority, unless the data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.¹⁹⁸ As soon as a controller becomes aware of a data breach, the controller should notify it to the supervisory authority without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it. Only when the controller is able to demonstrate, in accordance with the accountability principle, that the

¹⁹² Recital 85 of the GDPR

¹⁹³ Ibid p.6

¹⁹⁴G29 WP213, 25 March 2014, Opinion 03/2014 on Personal Data Breach Notification, p. 5, https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion_recommendation/index_en.htm#maincontentSec4

¹⁹⁵ G29 WP250 rev.1, 6 February 2018, Guidelines on Personal data breach notification under Regulation 2016/679 - endorsed by the EDPB, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/item-detail.cfm?item_id=612052.

¹⁹⁶ More recently the EDPB has issued new guidelines aimed at helping data controllers handling data breaches as well as their risk assessment See EDPB, 14 December 2021, Guidelines 01/2021 on Examples regarding Personal Data Breach Notification Version 2.0.

¹⁹⁷ Article 33 (5). Of the GDPR

¹⁹⁸ Article 33(1) of the GDPR

personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, no notification is required.¹⁹⁹ The notification to the supervisory authority must at least contain the following details:

- a. describe the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned;
 - b. communicate the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained;
 - c. describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach;
 - d. describe the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects.
- iii. Communicate the personal data breach to the data subject when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.²⁰⁰ The obligation to inform the data subject must be done without undue delay when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. The communications needs to be clear and in plain language, include the nature of the personal data breach and at least the same information provided to the supervisory authority. The same article 34 indicates an exhaustive exempts the controller's obligation to inform the data subject when:
- a. The controller has implemented appropriate technical and organisational measures
 - b. The controller has taken subsequent measures ensuring that the high risk to the rights and freedoms will not materialise
 - c. Informing to the data subjects would imply a disproportionate effort

In the context of the personal data stored at the MES-CoBraD platform, the technical and organisational measures adopted will determine the protocol of communication during the research activities. It is recommended that the implementation of data breach notification protocols is translated into the elaboration of a "Handbook on Handling Personal Data Breach."²⁰¹

4.8 DATA SUBJECT RIGHTS UNDER THE GDPR

The rights of the data subjects are listed in articles 13-21 of the GDPR:

- a. The right to information
- b. The right to access the data
- c. The right to rectification
- d. The right to erasure (the right to be forgotten)
- e. The right to restriction of processing
- f. The right to data portability
- g. The right to object

It is again necessary to distinguish between the different responsibilities and processing activities taking in place at MES-CoBraD. Medical partners remain individual controllers for the personal data stored at their premises, thus are fully responsible for the observance of data subject rights in light of EU and national laws. From the other hand, the derogations provided in the special regime applies to the processing of personal data at the platform, taking into consideration the distribution of responsibilities

¹⁹⁹ Recital 85 of the GDPR

²⁰⁰ Article 34 (1) of the GDPR

²⁰¹ Supra

between partners.

The following sections provide an overview on data subject rights in the context of MES-CoBraD.

4.8.1 THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION

The right to information is observed in two articles, Articles 13 and 14. of the GDPR. Article 13 regulates the case where personal data is collected directly from the data subject while Article 14 applies in those cases where data comes from other sources. In the case of data processing from patient records or the processing of data from other countries article 14 applies.

The disclosure of information to data subjects on the processing activities represents a practical consequence of the principles of fair and transparent processing. It supposes a fundamental pre-requisite for the compliance of the controller’s data protection obligation as it enables data subjects to invoke their data subject rights should they wish to do so.²⁰²

In light of the right to information, at the time of collection, the controller is obliged to provide the data subject the following details regarding the processing:

Right to information – information to be provided Article 13(1) and 14 (1) of the GDPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the identity and the contact details of the controller and, where applicable, of the controller's representative. (b) the contact details of the data protection officer, where applicable. (c) the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing; (d) where the processing is based on point (f) of Article 6(1), the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party; (e) the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data, if any; (f) where applicable, the fact that the controller intends to transfer personal data to a third country or international organisation and the existence or absence of an adequacy decision by the Commission, or in the case of transfers referred to in Article 46 or 47, or the second subparagraph of Article 49(1), reference to the appropriate or suitable safeguards and the means by which to obtain a copy of them or where they have been made available.
---	--

Further additional information the controller will need to present to the data subject upon collecting his or her personal data when that is needed to ensure transparency and fairness:

Right to information – further information to be provided Article 13(2) and 14 (2) of the GDPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the period for which the personal data will be stored, or if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period; (b) the existence of the right to request from the controller access to and rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing concerning the data subject or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability; (c) where the processing is based on point (a) of Article 6(1) or point (a) of Article 9(2), the existence of the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal; (d) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority; (e) whether the provision of personal data is a statutory or contractual requirement, or a requirement necessary to enter into a contract, as well as whether the data subject is obliged to provide the personal data, and of the possible consequences of failure to provide such data; (f) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic
---	---

²⁰² Due to its enabling nature, the applicability of exemptions on the right to information for the data stored in the MES-CoBraD platform, have a direct impact on the exercise of data subject’s rights.

	involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.
--	---

At the time of collection, medical partners will have to inform the data subject about the further processing that will take place following to their national laws and applicable codes. At least in the case of prospective data, the data subject should be provided, prior to that further processing takes place, with information on that other purpose and with any additional information.²⁰³

With regards to the processing of personal data taking place at the MES-CoBraD platform, the exemptions of Article (14) (5) of the GDPR must be considered. Considering the de-personalisation safeguards as well as the commitment of non-re-identification, it is particularly relevant the exemption based. the impossibility or disproportionate effort of informing the data subject.²⁰⁴ In this respect, the EDBP considers as an example of “disproportionate effort the case where “a large number of data subjects where there is no available contact information²⁰⁵.

4.8.2 THE RIGHT TO ACCESS THE DATA

The right of access, provided in article 15 of the GDPR has the objective of facilitating data subjects’ verification of the lawfulness of a processing activity using his or her personal data. As the right to information, the right of access has also an instrumental nature when it comes to exercising other data subject’s rights such as the rectification, erasure or blocking of personal data²⁰⁶. Pursuant the right of access, the data subject will have the right to obtain the following information:

<p>Right of access</p> <p>Article 15 of the GDPR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the purposes of the processing; (b) the categories of personal data concerned; (c) the recipients or categories of recipient to whom the personal data have been or will be disclosed, in particular recipients in third countries or international organisations; (d) where possible, the envisaged period for which the personal data will be stored, or, if not possible, the criteria used to determine that period; (e) the existence of the right to request from the controller rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing of personal data concerning the data subject or to object to such processing; (f) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority; (g) where the personal data is not collected from the data subject, any available information as to their source; (h) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.
--	--

In terms of limitations, the right of access is expressly delineated by the rights and freedoms of others. Despite the fact that data subjects are not obliged to give reasons or to justify their request, the same can be restricted when a request is manifestly unfounded or excessive.²⁰⁷ However and without prejudice to the existence of national rules on specific areas (i.e. law enforcement or health data), as long as the requirements of Article 15 of the GDPR are met, the purposes behind the request should be regarded as

²⁰³ Article 13(3) and 14(4) of the GDPR

²⁰⁴ (Article 14(5) b of the GDPR: Proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort”.

²⁰⁵ EDPB 03/2020 p. 9 . See also reference to See the Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679 of the former Article-29 Working-Party from 11.4.2018, WP260 rev.01, 17/EN, page 29 (endorsed by the EDPB). Available at https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/item-detail.cfm?item_id=622227b .

²⁰⁶ CJEU, Joined Cases C-141/12 and C-372/12, YS, and Others.

²⁰⁷ Article 12 (5) of the GDPR

irrelevant.

4.8.3 THE RIGHT TO ERASURE (RIGHT TO BE FORGOTTEN)

The right to erasure, alternatively known as the right to be forgotten is provided in Article 17 of the GDPR. The right to erasure grants individuals the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning him or her without undue delay where one of the following grounds applies:

<p>The right to erasure</p> <p>Article 17 of the GDPR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the personal data are no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were collected or otherwise processed; (b) the data subject withdraws consent on which the processing is based according to point (a) of Article 6(1), or point (a) of Article 9(2), and where there is no other legal ground for the processing; (c) the data subject objects to the processing pursuant to Article 21(1) and there are no overriding legitimate grounds for the processing, or the data subject objects to the processing pursuant to Article 21(2); (d) the personal data have been unlawfully processed; (e) the personal data have to be erased for compliance with a legal obligation in Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject; (f) the personal data have been collected in relation to the offer of information society services referred to in Article 8(1).
---	--

The right to erasure is not absolute, and in the context of scientific research, derogations are observed in article 17 (3) of the GDPR. The data subject’s right is limited in those cases where its enforcement would be likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement the research objectives. This is particularly relevant for that personal data unlawfully processed or no longer necessary in relation to the purpose for which they were collected, or when the data subject has withdrawn his/her consent.

Only the relevant medical partner remains capable of re-identifying a data subject whose data is at MES-CoBraD platform, based on the data stored at its premisses. Insofar that data at the clinical site is deleted, the pseudonymised information at the MES-CoBraD platform should in principle become anonymous.

4.8.4 THE RIGHT TO RESTRICTION OF THE PROCESSING

Based on Article 18 of the GDPR, the data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller restriction of processing where one of the following applies:

- (a) the accuracy of the personal data is contested by the data subject, for a period enabling the controller to verify the accuracy of the personal data;
- (b) the processing is unlawful, and the data subject opposes the erasure of the personal data and requests the restriction of their use instead;
- (c) the controller no longer needs the personal data for the purposes of the processing, but they are required by the data subject for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims;
- (d) the data subject has objected to processing pursuant to Article 21(1) pending the verification whether the legitimate grounds of the controller override those of the data subject.

The term “restriction” is not defined in the GDPR. The scope of this right is the limitation of the controller’s capacity to process personal data. Examples of measures that might facilitate the right to restriction include inter alia (Recital 67): temporarily moving the selected data to another processing system, making the selected personal data unavailable to users, or temporarily removing published data from a website.

In automated filing systems such as MES-CoBraD, controllers should be able to restrict the processing of data by technical means in such a manner that the personal data are not subject to further processing operations and cannot be changed. The status of restricted data should be clearly indicated in the system.

4.8.5 THE RIGHT TO PORTABILITY

The right to data portability is observed in Article 20 of the GDPR. It grants the data subject the right to receive the personal data concerning him or her, which he or she has provided to a controller, in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format and the right to transmit those data to another controller without hindrance from the controller to which the personal data have been provided. The right to data portability is provided to data subjects under two conditions, that the processing is based on consent or on a contract basis and that the processing is carried out by automated means.

As in the case of the right to information, insofar the datasets stored at MES-CoBraD are pseudonymised data, the right to data portability would be contentious. Implementing the right to portability in the design of the platform would force the controllers to technically contravene their commitment to not allow the re-identification from the data processed at the platform. Nevertheless, considering the exploitation objectives of the platform, the possibility from data subjects to transfer their data to another might be relevant.

4.8.6 THE RIGHT TO OBJECT

The right to object states that data subjects have, at any time, the right to deny, on grounds relating to his or her particular situation, to processing of personal data concerning him or her where the legal basis of the processing relies on public interests or legitimate interests.²⁰⁸

Data subjects do not have a general right to object to the processing of their data, but when it comes to the balancing interests, the burden of proof is vested in the controller. It is the controller who will need to show “compelling and “legitimate” grounds for continuing processing the data.²⁰⁹ In the event the interests of data subject override those of the controller, the exercise of the right to object will force the controller to stop the processing of personal data.²¹⁰

4.9 DESIGNATION OF DATA PROTECTION OFFICER AND DECLARATION OF COMPLIANCE

In May 2021, a month after the official launch of the project, all members of the MES-CoBraD were requested to provide the details of their nominated Data Protection Officer (DPO) or contact point for MES-CoBraD legal and ethical matters. Moreover, all partners were also requested to sign an acknowledgement statement concerning their obligations towards national and EU legislation, including but not limited to compliance with the GDPR.²¹¹

4.9.1 DESIGNATION OF A DATA PROTECTION OFFICER (DPO).

The DPO is a multidisciplinary role found in the GDPR and other EU data protection instruments. Defined as a cornerstone of accountability, DPOs are entrusted with the organisation’s compliance of its data protection obligations while also function as intermediaries between the appointing organisations, the supervisory authority, and the data subjects.²¹²

The DPO is a role performed by an expert on data protection law, appointed by an organisation, institution, or public authority, following their obligations as controllers of the data processing operations carried out

²⁰⁸ Article 21 of the GDPR

²⁰⁹ Recital 69 of the GDPR

²¹⁰ In the case *Cammerla de Commercio v Salvatore Manni* the CJEU considered that national courts have the responsibility to assess the individual circumstances on a case-by-case basis.

²¹¹ The nomination of data protection (DPO) in MES-CoBraD and the declaration of compliance regarding the processing of personal data. Submitted on 13 May 2021. Section 2.5.4 of the Data Management Plan; A signed copy of the documents is stored at the MES-Cobrad Sharepoint.

²¹² See WP29, 5 April 2017, Guidelines on Data Protection Officers (‘DPOs’), 16/EN WP 243 rev.01

during the course of their activities. Its designation is mandatory in three cases: i) where a public authority carries out a processing activity; where the controller’s or processor’s main activity involve the systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale or where the core activities consist of large-scale processing of special categories of data (i.e health data,) or data concerning criminal convictions.²¹³

Pursuant to their normative framework all partners in MES-CoBraD have nominated a DPO and/or provided the details of the contact person for legal and ethical matters in the context of the project’s research activities.²¹⁴

4.9.2 DECLARATION OF COMPLIANCE

All partners in MES-CoBraD have signed a “Declaration of compliance regarding the processing of personal data” declaring that “the collection and processing of personal data in the project, within the activities involving the [relevant partner], is or will be carried out according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (the General Data Protection Regulation), and the national law of the country where the partner organisation is established”.²¹⁵

Therefore, it is acknowledged that partners acting as data controllers and processors have taken all the necessary measures for their internal GDPR compliance and safeguarded all personal data. This is particularly relevant with regards to the role of medical partners and the processing activities on health data taking place at their premises. The individual responsibilities of each partner do not liberate the obligation of the MES-CoBraD to comply with its obligations as a research project.

4.10 INTERNATIONAL DATA TRANSFERS AND ADEQUACY DECISIONS

<p>Transfers on the basis of an adequacy decision</p> <p>Article 45 of the GDPR; Recital 103</p>	<p>1.A transfer of personal data to a third country or an international organisation may take place where the Commission has decided that the third country, a territory or one or more specified sectors within that third country, or the international organisation in question ensures an adequate level of protection. Such a transfer shall not require any specific authorisation</p> <p>(...)</p>
--	---

Article 45 of the GDPR regulates the most convenient mechanism to transfer data to third countries outside the European Economic Area (EEA).²¹⁶ In light of article 45 of the GDPR, the European Commission is competent to issue “adequacy decisions”, declaring whether a third country offers an adequate level of data Protection.²¹⁷

When an adequacy decision is still in force, controllers do not need to take additional measures regarding the data transfer, providing that all other aspects of the Regulation are respected.²¹⁸ In practice, adequacy decision allows that personal data flow from the EEA to that third country without any additional transfer tool being necessary.²¹⁹

²¹³ Article 37 of the GDPR.

²¹⁴ *ibid*

²¹⁵ *ibid*

²¹⁶ European Economic Area and it includes the Member States of the European Union and Iceland, Norway, and Liechtenstein. The GDPR applies to the latter by virtue of the EEA Agreement, in particular its Annex XI and Protocol 37.

²¹⁷

²¹⁸ Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data Version 2.0 Adopted on 18 June 2021

²¹⁹ EDPB Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data, accessible at https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2020/recommendations-012020-measures-supplement_en (Last accessed 20 February 2022).

However, it must be noted that adequacy decisions do not prevent data subjects from filing a complaint against controllers. In a similar vein, they do not prevent supervisory authorities from bringing a case before a national court whenever there are doubts on the validity of a decision, so that a national court can make a reference for a preliminary ruling to the CJEU for the purpose of examining that validity.²²⁰

In the case Schrems II, the CJEU reminds that the protection granted to personal data in the EEA must travel with the data wherever it goes. Transferring personal data to third countries cannot be a means to undermine or water down the protection it is afforded in the EEA. The Court clarifies that the level of protection in third countries does not need to be identical to that guaranteed within the EEA but essentially equivalent.²²¹ In connection to this, in 2021 the EDPB adopted the Guidelines on codes of conducts as tools for transfers. The guidelines are specifically aimed at dealing with the issue of codes of conduct as appropriate safeguards for transfers of personal data to third countries in accordance with Article 46.2(e) of the GDPR.²²²

To the extent that the MES-CoBraD platform envisages the flow of datasets from third countries, the development of a code of conduct should be taken into account. This aspect will be further elaborated in the D.2.9 of the Ethical and Normative Framework.v 2.

4.10.1 ARE THERE DATA TRANSFERS IN MES-COBRA D ?

The MES-CoBraD project might potentially transfer personal data to third-party countries, namely Israel and the United Kingdom. Both countries have been granted an adequacy decision by the European Commission.

As indicated in the first version of the Data Management Plan (see section 2.5.3), “the project will keep track and map the existence of data transfers and ensure that the research conducted outside the EU does not contravene the legal standards set by the EU.” In order to do so, next versions of the data management plan will, with the collaboration of all medical partners, record and map any potential transfers with third countries, and, when appropriate, indicate any a series of processors and sub-processors. This is an essential first step to fulfil the Project’s obligations under the principle of accountability. Regarding the potential exploitation of the platform, the access and process by users of MES-CoBraD from outside the EU/EEA should be further assessed.

In terms of territoriality, they however only cover whether personal data can leave the EU, which raises the question about what occurs for the data entering the EU from a third country.

4.11 DATA PROTECTION IMPACT ASSESSMENT

One of the main novelties introduced by the GDPR is the obligation for the data controller to conduct the process of data protection impact assessment (DPIA) before starting to process personal data. DPIAs aim to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with the law. whenever an envisaged data processing activity is likely to result in a “high risk” to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.²²³ As such it reflects the risk-based approach to the protection of personal data in the reformed

²²⁰ Oskar Josef Gstrein and Andrej Janko Zwitter, ‘Extraterritorial Application of the GDPR: Promoting European Values or Power?’, *Internet Policy Review* 10, no. 3 (30 September 2021), <https://policyreview.info/articles/analysis/extraterritorial-application-gdpr-promoting-european-values-or-power>.

²²¹ Supra 216. The Court also upheld the validity of standard contractual clauses, as a transfer tool that may serve to ensure contractually an essentially equivalent level of protection for data transferred to third countries.

²²² EDPB, 14 July 2021, Guidelines 04/2021 on codes of conduct as tools for transfer; accessible at https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2021/guidelines-042021-codes-conduct-tools-transfers_en; (last accessed 20 February 2022); Previously on 15 December 2020, the EDPB had adopted guidelines for international data transfers between public bodies in application of Articles 46 paragraph 2a and 46 paragraph 3b GDPR.

²²³ Article 35 (1) and article 35(7) of the GDPR.

EU legal framework and its principle of accountability.

In light of the data processing operations envisaged at the MES-CoBraD platform it is recommended that prior the deployment of the platform a DPIA is commissioned.

The content of the current document provides relevant details for several steps of the process of the DPIA as interpreted from articles 35-36 of the GDPR:²²⁴

1. The screening of the need to conduct the assessment,
2. The description of processing operations both from a contextual and technical perspective,
3. The appraisal of impacts.
4. Formulation of recommendations including measures to address risks and demonstrate compliance

The updated version of this deliverable (D2.9), as well as the rest of tasks in WP2 will continue the work and follow up the how the MES-CoBraD platform will eventually deal with GDPR requirements.

²²⁴ Kloza, Dariusz, Niels van Dijk, Simone Casiraghi, Sergi Vazquez Maymir, Sara Roda, Alessia Tanas and Ioulia Konstantinou (2019) "Towards a method for data protection impact assessment: Making sense of GDPR requirements", d.pia.lab Policy Brief No. 1/2019, VUB: Brussels. https://cris.vub.be/files/48091346/dpialab_pb2019_1_final.pdf

5 MES-COBRA D AS A MEDICAL DEVICE

The main instrument of the EU framework regarding medical devices, is the EU Medical Devices Regulation (MD Regulation)²²⁵, which entered into force in 2017, and is applicable since 26 May 2020. The MD Regulation aims to harmonise the rules and procedures related to medical devices. Considering the MES-CoBraD project's utilisation of various existing technologies as well as the development of the MES-CoBraD platform itself, the EU Medical Devices Regulation is relevant.²²⁶

5.1.1 SCOPE OF "MEDICAL DEVICES"

The MD Regulation defines a medical devices as: "(...) any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes:

- › diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment, or alleviation of disease,
- › diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability,
- › investigation, replacement, or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state,
- › providing information by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood, and tissue donations."²²⁷

Software is clearly mentioned in the definition. To qualify as a medical device, however, it is important that the manufacturer intended the software to be used for one of those medical purposes, e.g., monitoring diagnostic and/or therapeutic purposes. In contrast, a device that *de facto* performs an activity that falls within the letter of the definition but is not intended to be used for medical purposes by its manufacturer, is not a medical device. Accordingly, the safety certification as a medical device cannot be required. In light of the Brain Products GmbH v BioSemi VOF and Others cases,²²⁸ the CJEU sustained that a medical device must satisfy the essential requirements of the (replaced) directive and bear the CE marking, only if its manufacturer expressly intended to market it for medical purposes.

The recently updated Manual on Borderline and Classification in the Community Regulatory Framework for medical devices²²⁹, attempts to provide some clarification when the assessment of a solution as a medical device is unclear. It is important to underline that these guidance documents are not legally binding.

5.1.2 MES-COBRA D AS A MEDICAL DEVICE

The MES-CoBraD project aims to develop a platform that fuses RWD data collected from various sources to diagnose and ultimately treat complex brain disorders. The MES-CoBraD Platform is not merely intended to store data but to exploit it for an assessment. As such, it allows the utilisation of data beyond

²²⁵ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices; accessible at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017R0745>

²²⁶ TENDER D1.1 section 5

²²⁷ Article 2 of the Regulation (EU) 2017/745

²²⁸ Judgment of the Court (Third Chamber), 22 November 2012 Brain Products GmbH v BioSemi VOF and Others, C-219/11 - Brain Products - accessible at <http://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-219/11&language=EN>

²²⁹ Manual on Borderline and Classification in the Community Regulatory Framework for medical devices, version 1.18. <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/35582>

storage and for the medical benefit of the patient. Considering the discussed above, it might be important for partners to declare clearly whether the MES-CoBraD platform will eventually be exploited for (among others) medical purposes.

This might require a MES-CoBraD platform to a stricter series of safety controls than a non-medical device would require. This aspect will be followed up in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This document has captured the Ethical and Regulatory framework of MES-CoBraD at the date of writing. The content and recommendations herein presented will need to be mobilised by the partners during the remaining duration of the project. Because some of the issues discussed are intricately linked to the development of the project's research activities, their monitoring and follow up will be necessary.

Ethical framework next steps:

- › Follow up the practical implementation of the framework in the context of T2.2 The CoBraD PUC legal and ethical assessment and its results in D2.5, Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards- v1 and in D2.8 Final Assessment of the CoBraD PUCs against ethical and legal standards -v2.
- › In the context of governance ethics, continue to monitor potential ethical questions that arise in the development of the MES-CoBraD platform.

Regulatory framework next steps:

- › Monitor and when necessary complete the list of data processing activities and its description will during the course of the project. Report findings in in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2.
- › Monitor the completion of the data processing arrangement between partners. Report findings in in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2
- › Monitor the implementation of the key design and default features identified in section 10, Report findings in in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2
- › Monitor and identify new risks that could impact the personal data processed during the project and report on those that could appear in a scenario of deployment. Report findings in in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2.
- › Monitor the development of data breach protocols in the context of the project research activities. Report findings in in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2
- › The development of a code of conduct regarding future international transfers of data into the MES-CoBraD platform will be further elaborated in the D.2.9 of the Ethical and Normative Framework v2.
- › Generally speaking, D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2. as well as the rest of tasks in WP2 will follow up how the MES-CoBraD platform will eventually deal with GDPR requirements.
- › Examine how the MES-CoBraD platform might fall into the scope of the Medical Device Regulation. This aspect will be followed up in D.2.9 Ethical and Normative Framework v2.

7 REFERENCES

- Alan F. Westin, (1968. *Privacy And Freedom*, 25 Wash. & Lee L. Rev. 166. Retrieved from <https://scholarlycommons.law.wlu.edu/wlulr/vol25/iss1/20>
- Article WP29. (2017) Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on October 2017, Retrieved from
- Article WP29. (2017) Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 28 November 2017. Endorsed by the EDPB. Retrieved from
- Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works.’ (1886). Retrieved from <https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/ip/berne/index.html>.
- Bert-Jaap Koops et al., «A Typology of Privacy», SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 24 March 2016), <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2754043>
- Brill. ‘European Journal of Health Law Volume 25 Issue 5: Biobanking Edited by Anne-Marie Duguet and Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag (2018)’. Retrieved from. <https://brill.com/view/journals/ejhl/25/5/ejhl.25.issue-5.xml>.
- British Medical Journal. The New EU Regulation on the Protection of Personal Data: What Does It Mean for Patients?’, n.d., 23.
- Chassang, Gauthier, and Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag. (2018) ‘Research Biobanks and Health Databases: The WMA Declaration of Taipei, Added Value to European Legislation (Soft and Hard Law).’ *European Journal of Health Law* 25, no. 5 501–16. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12255369>.
- Chcuk. (2021) ‘Non-Interventional Study | Non-Interventional Trial | NIS - CHCUK Ltd.’ Retrieved from. <https://www.chcuk.co.uk/non-interventional-studies/>.
- Council of Europe, (1981) *Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data*, CETS No. 08, 28 January 1981. Retrieved from <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/108>
- Council of Europe. (1950). *European Convention on Human Rights*, CETS No. 005, 1950. Retrieved from https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf.
- Council of Europe. (1997). *Recommendation No. R (97) 5 on the Protection of Medical Data*’. Retrieved from <http://hrlibrary.umn.edu/instreet/coerecr97-5.html>.
- Council of Europe. (2005) ‘Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, Concerning Biomedical Research.’ *Jahrbuch Für Wissenschaft Und Ethik* 10, no. 1 (17 January 2005). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110182521.391>.
- Council of Europe. Treaty Office. ‘Full List.’. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list>.
- Court Judgment (CJEU), Joined Cases C-141/12 and C-372/12, YS, and Others.
- Czarska-Thorley, Dagmara. ‘Workshop on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Secondary Use of Data for Medicines Public Health Purposes.’ Text. European Medicines Agency, 14 July 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/events/workshop-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr-secondary-use-data-medicines-public-health-purposes>.
- D.Markopoulou, E.Papakonstantinou. Vrije Universiteit Brussels (2021), D6.5 – Data governance and ETL specifications -Preliminary Version, Fact-based personalised nutrition for the young: (“Nutrishield”); Retrieved from <https://nutrishield-project.eu/>
- Data Saves Lives. ‘Case Study Alzheimer’s Disease.’ Retrieved from. <https://datasaveslives.eu/case-study-alzheimer>.

Dijk, Niels van, Simone Casiraghi, and Serge Gutwirth.(2021). 'The "Ethification" of ICT Governance. *Artificial Intelligence and Data Protection in the European Union.*' *Computer Law & Security Review* 43: 105597. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2021.105597>.

Donnelly, Mary, and Maeve McDonagh. (2019) 'Health Research, Consent and the GDPR Exemption.' *European Journal of Health Law* 26, no. 2 97–119. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12262427>.

European Commission, (2019), *Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, Publications Office*, Retrieved from <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/177365>

European Commission.(2018). *Ethics and data protection*; Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-data-protection_en.pdf

European Data Protection Board (2021). *Guidelines 04/2021 on Codes of Conduct as Tools for Transfers*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2021/guidelines-042021-codes-conduct-tools-transfers_en.

European Data Protection Board, (2019). *EDPB Guidelines 1/2019 on Codes of Conduct and Monitoring Bodies under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 12 February 2019*; Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb20190219_guidelines_coc_public_consultati_on_version_en.pdf.

European Data Protection Board, (2019). *EDPB Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default Adopted on 13 November 2019*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2019/guidelines-42019-article-25-data-protection_en

European Data Protection Board, (2020). *EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Adopted on 4 May 2020*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_guidelines_202005_consent_en.pdf

European Data Protection Board, (2021). *EDPB Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, Adopted on 07 July 2021*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-072020-concepts-controller-and-processor-gdpr_en

European Data Protection Board, (2021). *EDPB Guidelines 10/2020 on restrictions under Article 23 GDPR, Adopted on 13 October 2021*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-102020-restrictions-under-article-23-gdpr_en

European Data Protection Board, (2021.) *EDPB Guidelines 01/2021 on Examples regarding Data Breach Notification, Adopted on 19 January 2021*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2021/guidelines-012021-examples-regarding-data-breach_en

European Data Protection Board, European Data Protection Supervisor. (2021). *Joint Opinion 5/2021 on the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act). Adopted on 18 June 2021*. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-06/edpb-edps_joint_opinion_ai_regulation_en.pdf

European Data Protection Board,(2020). *EDPB Guidelines 03/2020 on the processing of data concerning health for the purpose of scientific research in the context of the COVID-19 outbreak, Adopted on 21 April 2020*, Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-032020-processing-data-concerning-health-purpose_en

European Data Protection Board. (2019). 'Opinion 3/2019 Concerning the Questions and Answers on the Interplay between the Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR) and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)'.

Text., 1 February 2019. Retrieved from https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/dictamen-art-70/opinion-32019-concerning-questions-and-answers_en.

European Data Protection Supervisor, (2020). *EDPS, A Preliminary Opinion on data protection and scientific research, Adopted on 6 January 2020* European Data Protection Supervisor. Retrieved from https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/20-01-06_opinion_research_en.pdf.

European Data Protection Supervisor. (2020). *EDPS Public Paper on Outcome of Own-Initiative Investigation into EU Institutions' Use of Microsoft Products and Services.*, 2020. Retrieved from https://op.europa.eu/publication/manifestation_identifier/PUB_QT0320457ENN.

European Law Blog. (2020). 'Covid-19: A New Struggle over Privacy, Data Protection and Human Rights?', 4 May 2020. Retrieved from <https://europeanlawblog.eu/2020/05/04/covid-19-a-new-struggle-over-privacy-data-protection-and-human-rights/>.

European Medical Agency (2018). 'Clinical Trials Regulation.' Text. European Medicines Agency, 17 September 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/research-development/clinical-trials/clinical-trials-regulation>.

European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2014). *Guidance Document on the Scope of Application and Core Obligations of Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Compliance Measures for Users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from Their Utilisation in the Union*, n.d., 19.

European Parliament and Council of the European Union.(2016) *Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union (NIS Directive)*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/TodayOJ/>

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, (2011). *Directive 2011/24/EU on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare*, 088 OJ L § (2011). Retrieved from <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2011/24/oj/eng>.

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. (1995) *Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and the free flow of such data*.

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. (2018). *Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union (Text with EEA relevance.)*, Pub. L. No. 32018R1807, 303 OJ L (2018). Retrieved from <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2018/1807/oj/eng>.

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union.(2014) *Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 of 16 April 2014 on compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization in the Union*.

European Parliament, Council and Commission,(2000). *Charter on Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, 7 December 2000. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>

European Union Agency for cybersecurity (ENISA). (2022) *Risk Management Standards*. Retrieved from; <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/risk-management-standards>

European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO)- *Home.*' Accessed 24 March 2022. <https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en>.

European Union, *Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*, 25 March 1957 (and as amended) ("TFEU"), Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:12016ME/TXT>

Fernandez Lynch, Holly, and Steven Joffe. (2019). 'Pay-to-Participate Trials and Vulnerabilities in Research Ethics Oversight.' *JAMA* 322, no. 16 (22 October 2019): 1553. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.14703>.

Floridi, L., & Cowls, J. (2019). *A Unified Framework of Five Principles for AI in Society*. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 1(1). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.8cd550d1>.

G. González Fuster,(2014). 'The Beginning of EU Data Protection', in *The Emergence of Personal Data Protection as a Fundamental Right of the EU*, ed. Gloria González Fuster, Law, Governance and Technology Series (Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2014), 111–62, Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05023-2_5.

Gerke, Sara, Timo Minssen, and Glenn Cohen.(2020). 'Ethical and Legal Challenges of Artificial Intelligence-Driven Healthcare.' *Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare*, 2020, 295–336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818438-7.00012-5>.

Habli I, Lawton T, Porter Z. (2020). Artificial intelligence in health care: accountability and safety. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2020;98(4):251-256. doi:10.2471/BLT.19.237487

Herman WH, Cohen RM. (2012). *Racial and ethnic differences in the relationship between HbA1c and blood glucose: implications for the diagnosis of diabetes*. 97(4):1067-72. doi: 10.1210/jc.2011-1894. Epub 2012 Jan 11. PMID: 22238408; PMCID: PMC3319188.

Herveg, Jean.(2018). 'Data Protection and Biobanks in 2018'. *European Journal of Health Law* 25, no. 5: 479–500. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12255410>.

European Parliament,.(2021) Intellectual, Industrial and Commercial Property Fact Sheets on the European Union. Retrieved from. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/36/intellectual-industrial-and-commercial-property>.

Judgement of the Court, (CJEU),(2018) Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz Schleswig-Holstein v Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein GmbH, Case C-210/16, ECLI:EU:C:2018:388'. Retrieved from <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?jsessionid=CE75151B26D18DA61DA837CFD2494A9D?text=&docid=202543&pageIndex=0&doclang=en&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=719312>.

Kaushal A, Altman R, Langlotz (2020). *Geographic Distribution of US Cohorts Used to Train Deep Learning Algorithms*. *JAMA*. 2020 Sep 22;324(12):1212-1213. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.12067. PMID: 32960230; PMCID: PMC7509620.

Kosta, E. (2013). *Consent in European data protection law*. (Nijhoff Studies in European Union Law; No. 3). Martinus Nijhoff.

Kuner, Christopher. (2021). 'Territorial Scope and Data Transfer Rules in the GDPR: Realising the EU's Ambition of Borderless Data Protection.' SSRN Scholarly Paper. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 16 April 2021. Retrieved from <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3827850>.

Lange, Dylan W. de, Bertrand Guidet, Finn H. Andersen, Antonio Artigas, Guidio Bertolini, Rui Moreno, Steffen Christensen, et al. (2019). 'Huge Variation in Obtaining Ethical Permission for a Non-Interventional Observational Study in Europe.' *BMC Medical Ethics* 20, no. 1 (December 2019): 39. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-019-0373-y>.

Leslie D, Mazumder A, Peppin A, Wolters M K, Hagerty (2021). A. Does "AI" stand for augmenting inequality in the era of covid-19 healthcare? *BMJ* 2021; 372 :n304 doi:10.1136/bmj.n304

London AJ.(2019). *Artificial Intelligence and Black-Box Medical Decisions: Accuracy versus Explainability*. *Hastings Cent Rep*. 2019 Jan;49(1):15-21. doi: 10.1002/hast.973. PMID: 30790315.

Lwoff, Laurence.(2020). 'New Technologies, New Challenges for Human Rights? The Work of the Council

of Europe.’ *European Journal of Health Law* 27, no. 3 (16 April 2020): 335–44. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-BJA10007>.

Mehrabi, Ninareh & Morstatter, Fred & Saxena, Nripsuta & Lerman, Kristina & Galstyan, Aram. (2019). A Survey on Bias and Fairness in Machine Learning. Obermeyer Z, Powers B, Vogeli C, Mullainathan S. *Dissecting racial bias in an algorithm used to manage the health of populations*. *Science*. 2019 Oct 25;366(6464):447-453. doi: 10.1126/science.aax2342. PMID: 31649194 .

Meulenbroek et al., *Informed Consent in Dementia research*. Legislation, Theoretical Concepts and How to Assess Capacity to Consent

Morley J, Machado CCV, Burr C, Cowls J, Joshi I, Taddeo M, Floridi L. (2020). *The ethics of AI in health care: A mapping review*. *Soc Sci Med*. 2020 Sep;260:113172. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113172. Epub 2020 Jul 15. PMID: 32702587.

Morley, Jessica, Caio C. V. Machado, Christopher Burr, Josh Cowls, Indra Joshi, Mariarosaria Taddeo, and Luciano Floridi. (2020). ‘*The Ethics of AI in Health Care: A Mapping Review*.’ *Social Science & Medicine* 260 (1 September 2020): 113172. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113172>.

Nadezhda Purtova, (2018). ‘The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law,’ *Law, Innovation, and Technology* 10(1) (2018).

Norori, N., Hu, Q., Aellen, F. M., Faraci, F. D., & Tzovara, A. (2021). *Addressing bias in big data and AI for health care: A call for open science*. *Patterns* (New York, N.Y.), 2(10), 100347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100347>.

Obermeyer Z, Powers B, Vogeli C, Mullainathan S. (2019) *Dissecting racial bias in an algorithm used to manage the health of populations*. *Science*. 2019;366(6464):447–53

OECD, 1980 *Guidelines Governing the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data*. An updated version was adopted in 2013. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/sti/ieconomy/oecdguidelinesontheProtectionofPrivacyandTransborderFlowsOfPersonalData.htm> (Last accessed on 21 March 2022).

P. Boddington, L. Curren, J. Kaye, N. Kanellopoulou, K. Melham, H. Gowansa and N. Hawkinsa, ‘Consent (2011). Forms in Genomics: The Difference between Law and Practice,’ *The European Journal of Health Law* 18 491-519

P. P. Craig and G. De Búrca, eds.,(2011). *The Evolution of EU Law*, 2nd ed (Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 2011).

P. Quinn, E. Mantovani, A. van Scharen. (Vrije Universiteit Brussels), PROTEIN, D10.1 *Report on security, data protection, privacy, consumer protection, ethics and social acceptance* (TARESS Framework) (2019) (“PROTEIN”); Personalised nutrition for healthy living: Protein; <https://protein-h2020.eu/>

P. Quinn, L. Feirabend Vrije Universiteit Brussels D1.1 – *Fundamental Rights, Ethical and Legal Implications and Assessment Affective based iNtegrated carE for better Quality of Life*: (“TeNDER”) Project; Retrieved from <https://www.alzheimer-europe.org/research/projects/affective-based-integrated-care-better-quality-life>

Panch, T., Mattie, H. & Celi, L.A. (2019) The “inconvenient truth” about AI in healthcare. *npj Digit. Med*. 2, 77. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-019-0155-4>;

Participant-Funded Clinical Trials on Rare Diseases | Elsevier Enhanced Reader.’ Retrieved from. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anpede.2020.03.005>.

Proceedings brought by Tietosuojavaltuutettu, No. Case C-25/17 (ECJ 10 July 2018).

Quinn, Paul, and Paul De Hert. (2011). 'The Patients' Rights Directive (2011/24/EU) – Providing (Some) Rights to EU Residents Seeking Healthcare in Other Member States'. *Computer Law & Security Review* 27, no. 5: 497–502. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2011.07.010>.

Quinn, Paul. (2017) 'The Anonymisation of Research Data – A Pyrrhic Victory for Privacy That Should Not Be Pushed Too Hard by the EU Data Protection Framework?' *European Journal of Health Law*, 2017, 22.

S. Rodotà, (2009). 'Data Protection as a Fundamental Right', in *Reinventing Data Protection?*, ed. Serge Gutwirth et al. (Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2009), 77–82, Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9498-9_3.

Samuel D. Warren & Louis D. Brandeis, (1890). *The Right to Privacy*, in *Harvard Law Review*, 1890, Vol. 4, No. 5, p 193-220.

Schnetzler, G. 'Interpretation of the Definition of Non-Interventional Trials under the Current Legislative Framework,' n.d., 18.

Slokenberga, Santa. (2018) 'Biobanking between the EU and Third Countries – Can Data Sharing Be Facilitated via Soft Regulatory Tools?' *European Journal of Health Law* 25, no. 5 (15 November 2018): 517–36. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12550397>.

Smith, H. (2021). *Clinical AI: opacity, accountability, responsibility, and liability*. *AI & Soc* 36, 535–545 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-020-01019-6>

Suresh, H., & Gutttag, J. (2021). *Understanding Potential Sources of Harm throughout the Machine Learning Life Cycle*. *MIT Case Studies in Social and Ethical Responsibilities of Computing*, (Summer 2021). <https://doi.org/10.21428/2c646de5.c16a07bb>

T. L. Beauchamp, J. F. Childress, (2010). *Principles of biomedical ethics*, Oxford University Press, USA, 2001; Walter, Klein eds. *The Story of Bioethics: From seminal works to contemporary explorations*; see also McLean S. *Autonomy, Consent, and the Law*. Routledge,

Taylor Wessing's Global Data Hub. *Selecting a Lawful Basis under the GDPR*. Retrieved from <https://globaldatahub.taylorwessing.com/article/clinical-trials-selecting-a-lawful-basis-under-the-gdpr>.

The Nuremberg Code.' Accessed 17 March 2022. Retrieved from <http://www.cirp.org/library/ethics/nuremberg/>.

Treaty on the European Union. Retrieved from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2bf140bf-a3f8-4ab2-b506-fd71826e6da6.0023.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

United Nations. (1948). Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 10 December 1948; Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

Verhenneman, G., K. Claes, J.J. Derèze, P. Herijgers, C. Mathieu, F.E. Rademakers, R. Reyda, and M. Vanautgaerden. 'How GDPR Enhances Transparency and Fosters Pseudonymisation in Academic Medical Research.' *European Journal of Health Law* 27, no. 1 (4 March 2020): 35–57. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12251009>.

WIPO, The International Design System.' Accessed 24 March 2022. <https://www.wipo.int/hague/en/index.html>.

WMA - The World Medical Association-WMA Declaration of Helsinki – *Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects*.' Retrieved from. <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>.

World Health Organization and Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences. *International Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research Involving Humans*. Geneva: CIOMS, 2017.

